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Report on the use of *in-silico* methods for the prioritisation of substances and mixtures thereof

WP 2– QSAR and TTC approaches for setting test priorities

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Deliverable D2.2

**Report on the use of *in-silico* methods for the
prioritisation of substances and mixtures thereof**

October 2016

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Report on the use of *in-silico* methods for the prioritisation of substances and mixtures thereof

Authors: Jane Cotterill¹, Ivano Eberini², Emiel Rorije³, Ad Peijnenburg⁴, Nick Price¹, Chris Ridgway¹

¹ Fera, Sand Hutton, York, UK; ² University of Milan, Italy; ³ RIVM, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, The Netherlands; ⁴ RIKILT, Wageningen University and Research Centre, The Netherlands

Introduction

The aim of task 2.2 was to attempt to establish a set of *in silico* procedures that would enable prediction of the endpoints of interest (CAG level 1: hepatotoxicity, developmental toxicity and endocrine disruption) where experimental data is not available and further to refine the toxicants CAG with additional information from the models e.g. phenomenological effect (CAG level 2) mode of action/mechanism of action (CAG levels 3 and 4). As an example of this the compounds predicted to be hepatotoxicants were sub-categorised into those likely to cause steatosis and those for which there was no evidence to suggest they would cause steatosis.

There are a number of different *in silico* techniques and approaches available to predict various properties and toxicity of compounds. The methods used in the project included a combination of predictive computational models based on Structure Activity Relationships (SAR), Quantitative Structure Activity Relationships (QSAR), expert systems and 3D molecular docking with key receptors. Some models predict the endpoints of interest at CAG level 1: e.g. hepatotoxicity, developmental toxicity, whilst others are more specific and predict effects at higher CAG levels, such as binding to key receptors e.g. ER, AR, LXR receptor binding.

For the hepatotoxicity endpoint there are a number of QSAR, Structural Alert and hybrid models available to predict hepatotoxicity in general and also more specifically, e.g. models which predict binding to nuclear receptors associated with steatosis (e.g. LXR, AhR and PPARgamma). QSAR and Structural Alert based models are available for the developmental toxicity endpoint, but there are fewer models available than the other endpoints and none specific for skeletal malformation, which is of interest to the project. For Endocrine Active substances a number of QSAR and Structural Alert models were identified, including many specific to Estrogen (ER), Androgen (AR) receptor binding. To predict if a compound is likely to be an ER or AR receptor binder, also binding energies were calculated using a 3D molecular docking technique.

The list of chemicals produced in task 2.1, were tested using the available suite of *in silico* models. As the range of chemicals considered in the project was very broad it was deemed unlikely that any single model

would suffice for all chemicals for a particular endpoint. A “weight of evidence” (WoE) approach was therefore taken, as recommended for regulatory predictive toxicology (Balls et al 2006, ECHA 2010). As a primary screen, to determine CAG level 1 membership, a simple majority voting scheme was used to determine a Consensus prediction. The performance of the individual models, as well as the Consensus of applicable models, was validated using test sets of compounds with known experimental activity (both positive and negative) for the endpoint in question, in order to determine the accuracy of the models and numbers of false positives and false negatives.

The predictive results of the (Q)SAR models provide CAG membership, however they do not give a quantitative prediction of the potency of a chemical. The molecular docking analyses are a promising tool as they provide quantitative results, and potency factors may be derived based on the binding energy of a molecule to the receptor. In task 2.3 for a first tier potency estimate other methodology will be applied (literature data, read across, TTC concept).

In task 2.2 a simple majority Consensus prediction generated using the results from the suite of *in silico* models was used as a first step. However, this decision scheme does not take into account the strengths and weaknesses of the underlying models. The uncertainty analyses of the final EuroMix approach should include the sensitivity/specificity/accuracy rate of the individual (Q)SAR method used. The next stage of the project, to be carried under task 2.4, will be to use the selected *in silico* models in a more refined decision scheme, based on Bayesian statistics. This would address both issues of taking into account strengths and weaknesses of individual models, and also give a chemical specific prediction of CAG membership with an associated uncertainty which can directly be used in a probabilistic way. This allows the “retain and refine” principle where in principle every chemical in the mixture is used for risk assessment, but the probability that a single substance will contribute significantly to the risk is different (very low for some substance, higher for others). It also combines well with the probabilistic treatment of the exposure data, giving a probability for combined exposure. The development of a more refined decision scheme using Bayesian statistics will be the focus of D2.4 in WP2.

Methods

The Chemical inventories produced in Task 2.1 were used as the source of chemicals with which to apply a range of *in silico* methods appropriate for the selected endpoints of interest in the EuroMix project. The various models were first applied to all suitable chemicals from the EuroMix Chemical Inventory_15-10-2015 version and at a later date when a large batch of new chemicals became available in Chemical

Inventory_19-07-2016 . In total there were 1101 chemicals to consider. Both versions of the Chemical Inventory are placed on the EuroMix Share.

The chemicals were run through a suite of *in silico* models and a majority weight of evidence prediction obtained (where at least half of the models provided a positive prediction then a positive prediction was assigned for a particular compound). Validation chemicals were chosen for the three endpoints and also run through the various models in order to determine the accuracy of the individual models and also the majority weight of evidence approach. As well as an overall prediction to assign the chemicals into a yes/no CAG membership for the three endpoints, further information from some of the models was produced to further categorise the positive compounds according to a mode / mechanism of action e.g. evaluation of the binding free energy of tested compounds through molecular docking. This process is described in more detail below.

Chemical Structures

The two-dimensional chemical structures are the required input for the suite of (Q)SAR models used in the project. These were downloaded as .mol files using ChemIDPlus (<http://chem.sis.nlm.nih.gov/chemidplus/>) searching on using the CAS number /chemical name from the 15-10-2015 or 19-07-2016 Chemical Inventory. As well as the chemical structures files, pictures of 2D structures, Molecular weight, Molecular Formula and Smiles codes were also obtained from ChemIDPlus and added to the database. In some cases, the chemical structure was not present in this database, but could be downloaded from Pubchem (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) or Chemspider (<http://www.chemspider.com/>).

As the correct chemical structure is vital for the correct *in silico* predictions, a quality check was carried out. All of the 2D structures obtained from ChemIDPlus were compared with those given by Pubchem. Where the PubChem and ChemIDPlus chemical structures were different, then Chemspider was also used. Where different structural isomers were provided using the different programs, the one most commonly presented was selected.

Not all chemical structures are suitable for (Q)SAR models e.g. metal complexes and salts, and so the next stage was to highlight any compounds in the chemical inventory not suitable for the *in silico* work. Where duplicates were present these were removed and if more than one stereoisomer was present just one was selected as only two-dimensional structures were being used. Only discrete organic chemicals can be used and so any mixtures and non-specific structures were removed. Any salts present were converted to the neutral parent structure to enable them to be used in the models. Details of any chemicals from the chemical inventory which were not suitable for the (Q)SAR models or are which were converted are provided in Annex 1.

Once all of the individual .mol structure files were obtained they were converted into an .sdf file to enable batch runs of the various *in silico* models. A final quality check was carried out on the chemical structures in the .sdf files. They were opened up in Multicase software (CASE Ultra v 1.5.2.0, www.multicase.com) and the 2D structures shown were compared with those downloaded from ChemIDplus in the database. In addition, some properties were calculated from the .sdf file using Discovery studio (v. 3.1, Accelrys) and the Molecular Weight and formula were checked with entries in database.

For the molecular docking work, all the .sdf file datasets were subsequently imported into the MOE Software (Chemical Computing Group) and saved as .mdb database. Each entry was processed using the MOE Database Viewer tool, in order to geometrically and energetically optimize structures for the subsequent molecular docking simulations. In detail, 2D structures were converted into 3D structures, the chirality of each compound was manually checked, and each structure was submitted to energy minimization, using the Amber10:EHT force field up to an RMS gradient of 0.05 [kcal/(mol Å²)] through the MOE Energy Minimize tool.

In silico models

Three main endpoints are being considered by the EuroMix project - Hepatotoxicity, Developmental toxicity and Endocrine Activity endpoints. The *in silico* models used to predict these endpoints are either freely available, or are commercial software for which EuroMix partners hold licenses for, and are shown in Table 1. In addition two QSAR models were developed at Fera for the project, to add to the weight of evidence to predict Hepatotoxicity and Estrogen receptor binding.

Table 1. (Q)SAR models used to predict the three endpoints in the EuroMix project

Model	Type of model	Hepatotoxicity	Developmental Toxicity	Endocrine Activity
COSMOS LXR binding QSAR models (two PLS-DA models are available built using different descriptors.)	QSAR	✓		
COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model	Structural Alert (SA)	✓		✓
DEREK Nexus	Structural Alert (SA) rule based expert	✓	✓	✓

Model	Type of model	Hepatotoxicity	Developmental Toxicity	Endocrine Activity
	system			
Fera c4.5 hepatotoxicity model using 4 CDK descriptors	QSAR	✓		
Fera c4.5 ER-binding QSAR model using 6 descriptors	QSAR			✓
MULTICASE Hepatotoxicity module	Hybrid (SA / QSAR)	✓		
OCHEM AhR and PPARgamma models	QSAR	✓		
OCHEM ER and AR agonist models (3 of both) and Aromatase inhibition model	QSAR			✓
OECD QSAR Toolbox DART scheme ER/AR alert	Structural Alert		✓	✓
OECD QSAR Toolbox ER-binding profiler	Structural Alert			✓
OECD QSAR Toolbox HESS alert	Structural Alert	✓		
OECD QSAR Toolbox rtER Expert system	Structural Alert			✓
PaDEL-DD Predictor	QSAR	✓		
Pizzo structural alert	Structural Alert	✓		
T.E.S.T. Developmental Toxicity model	QSAR		✓	
VEGA Developmental Toxicity (Caesar model)	QSAR		✓	
VEGA Developmental Toxicity (PG library model)	Structural Alert		✓	
VEGA RBA model	QSAR			✓

Unless otherwise stated the .sdf files for the different chemical types were used as input to the various models, which are described in more detail below.

COSMOS Models

Hepatotoxicity, in particular steatosis, was one of the endpoints considered by the recent COSMOS project (funded by the European Commission and Cosmetic Europe, www.cosmostox.eu). The aim of the project was to develop freely available tools and workflows to predict the safety of cosmetic ingredients. Three models relating to hepatotoxicity available from the project implemented into KNIME workflows are available in COSMOS KNIME WebPortal under Nuclear Receptor Binding. Two QSAR models predict LXR-binding potential and hence potential for hepatosteatois and a third model predicts binding to a number of Nuclear Receptor models important for hepatosteatois . These models were thus extremely useful in the *in silico* work package as steatosis is of particular interest to the EuroMix project.

COSMOS LXR-binding QSAR models:

Two QSAR classification models are available for the prediction of LXR binding potential, one a Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) model based on 6 PADEL descriptors and the second a PLS-DA model based on 5 RDKit descriptors.

At the time of writing, the LXR-binding QSAR model based on RDKit descriptors was not running (using either the .sdf file or a .csv file as input). As LXR binding is of great importance to the project, the training and test set compounds and algorithm were obtained from the authors and the QSAR model was reworked at Fera using Tanagra software (a free data mining tool, <http://eric.univ-lyon2.fr/~ricco/tanagra/en/tanagra.html>). The dataset used for model development consisted of 97 chemicals selected from a wider dataset of 356 known LXR binders (biological data and structure collected from the literature and available database). The dataset included 50 ligands characterized by an IC₅₀<20 nM, which were assigned to the ACTIVE class, and 47 ligands with an IC₅₀>1000 nM, which were assigned to the INACTIVE class. In addition to the active / inactive prediction for LXR-binding, applicability domain thresholds are produced as part of the output for Leverage and Similarity of the test compounds.

The second LXR-binding QSAR model (built using PADEL descriptors) ran on the WebPortal, however for the hepatotoxicity validation set, described in more detail below, the sensitivity was very poor and so the results from this model were not used in the Weight of Evidence. It is possible that the model is not working properly on the WebPortal.

COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model:

Nuclear receptors (NR) are an important target in toxicology, in particular when dealing with repeated doses. Agonists of certain nuclear receptor, e.g. RAR, RXR, LXR and PPAR, are associated with the development of fatty liver (hepatosteatosis), particularly in chronic exposure. To develop the model structural and physico-chemical features of NR ligands were investigated using data from ChEMBL and the Protein Data Bank (PDB). The obtained information is used in the prediction of potential NR ligands. ER and AR receptors are also built into the model so it is applicable to the Endocrine Activity endpoints as well as hepatotoxicity. Further details of the methodology of the workflow are available in a recent publication by Mellor et al 2016.

DEREK Nexus

DEREK Nexus is a rule-based expert system developed by Lhasa Limited, Leeds (<http://www.lhasalimited.org/products/derek-nexus.htm>). Structural alerts for a particular endpoint identify important structural fragments within molecules that are associated with specific toxicological effect and take into account toxicological and mechanistic evidence, and where appropriate metabolism and physicochemical properties of compounds. If a compound contains a Structural Alert then the likelihood that the compound will cause toxicity is provided (based on the species and other rules such as bioavailability). The likelihood of toxicity is given as either certain, probable, plausible, equivocal, doubted, improbable, impossible or contradicted). If no Structural Alert is fired then DEREK returns "Nothing to Report" (this does not necessarily mean a negative result, just that that the compound contains none of the structural fragments built into the rule based system). The output from DEREK Nexus is the likelihood of the compound causing the particular toxicological effect, an alert number & description of the toxicophore giving rise to the prediction.

Derek Nexus 5.01 contains 76 alerts for hepatotoxicity. Primary data used for alert development include repeat dose toxicity studies in animals, clinical case reports on liver toxicity and hepatotoxicity epidemiological studies. For the Developmental Toxicity endpoint the relevant alerts were 50 alerts for Teratogenicity and 4 alerts for Developmental Toxicity. For Endocrine active compounds there are 9 alerts for Oestrogen receptor modulation and 2 alerts for Oestrogenicity

Fera c4.5 model for hepatotoxicity using 5 CDK descriptors

In order to augment the available models available to predict hepatotoxicity a C4.5 decision tree model was developed at Fera using the dataset of Pizzo et al 2015. The model using 5 CDK descriptors (<http://www.rguha.net/code/java/cdkdesc.html>) was a c4.5 Decision tree built using TANAGRA (<http://eric.univ-lyon2.fr/~ricco/tanagra/>). Full details of the model are provided in Annex 2.

Fera c4.5 model for ER-binding using 6 RDKit descriptors

In order to augment the available models available to predict ER-binding a C4.5 decision tree model was developed at Fera using the Relative Binding Affinity training set using the VEGA model (www.vega-qsar.eu). The model using 6 RDKit descriptors (<http://www.rdkit.org/>) was a c4.5 Decision tree built using TANAGRA. Full details of the model are provided in Annex 3.

MULTICASE Hepatotoxicity bundle of models

The commercially available Multicase CASE Ultra Hepatotoxicity bundle (MultiCASE Inc, USA) contains six modules (RCA human acute liver damage, Human liver function tests, Human bile duct disorders, Human cholestasis, Human liver jaundice and Human gall bladder disorders). The CASE Ultra models identify structural alerts responsible for the observed activity. The database is then separated into groups of compounds based on the presence of each alert, and an analysis of each group is performed to identify possible QSARs. The models are thus based on Expert rules and Statistical based predictions. Each module provides a Prediction Call for activity as either positive, negative, inconclusive or out of domain along with a Probability of activity. As well as running the individual modules, there is a Consensus call allowing the user to select one of the following options:

- Majority: The predicted class that makes up more than half of the conclusive calls is used as the consensus call (clean Positive or Negative calls are considered conclusive calls). The consensus call becomes OUT OF DOMAIN if results against all individual models are 'OUT OF DOMAIN'. If positive and negative calls are exactly equal then the consensus call is NO CALL.
- Highest: If there are one or more positive calls amongst conclusive results then the consensus call is POSITIVE. If there are no positive calls but one or more negative calls are present amongst conclusive results then consensus call is NEGATIVE (Clean Positive or Negative calls are considered conclusive calls). The consensus call becomes OUT OF DOMAIN if results against all individual models are OUT OF DOMAIN.

Further details of the six models are provided below:

Liver Bile duct model (Version 1.5.2.0.1017.250) was developed using Human bile duct disorder response data (binary score units) from 1017 chemicals (141 active, 876 inactive) from Ursem et al 2009, Matthews et al 2009a and b and Zhu et al 2014 and has a classification threshold of 0.250. Chemicals were classed as Active with activity above 0.7 and inactive when activity was less than 0.3.

Liver Cholestasis model (Version 1.5.2.0.1124.300) was developed using Human cholestasis response data (binary score units) from 1124 chemicals (317 active, 807 inactive) from Ursem et al 2009, Matthews et al 2009a and b and Zhu et al 2014 and has a classification threshold of 0.3.

Liver damage model (Version 1.5.2.0.1314.500) was developed using Human acute liver damage response data (binary score units) from 1314 chemicals (661 active, 653 inactive) from Ursem et al 2009, Matthews et al 2009a and b and Zhu et al 2014 and has a classification threshold of 0.50. Chemicals were classed as Active with activity above 0.7 and inactive when activity was less than 0.3.

Liver function test (Version 1.5.2.0.1134.450) was developed using Human liver function test (blood test on liver enzymes release) response data (binary score units) from 1134 chemicals (435 active, 699 inactive) from Ursem et al 2009, Matthews et al 2009a and b and Zhu et al 2014 and has a classification threshold of 0.45. Chemicals were classed as Active with activity above 0.7 and inactive when activity was less than 0.3.

Liver Gall bladder model (Version 1.5.2.0.1050.250) was developed using Human gall bladder disorders response data (binary score units) from 1050 chemicals (160 active, 250 marginal and 640 inactive) from Ursem et al 2009 and Matthews et al 2009a and b and has a classification threshold of 0.25. Chemicals were classed as Active with activity above 0.7 and inactive when activity was less than 0.3 and marginal between 0.3 and 0.7.

Liver Jaundice model (Version 1.5.2.0.1586.250) was developed using Human liver jaundice response data (binary score units) from 1586 chemicals (237 active, 523 marginal and 826 inactive) from Ursem et al 2009 and Matthews et al 2009a and b and has a classification threshold of 0.25. Chemicals were classed as Active with activity above 0.7 and inactive when activity was less than 0.3 and marginal between 0.3 and 0.7.

OCHEM ER, AR, AhR and PPAR gamma agonist models

In the Tox21 Data Challenge 2014, data from a library of compounds screened experimentally in High-throughput screening (HTS) assays was made available for use in a modelling competition (Tox 21 2014, Abdelaziz et al 2016). The QSAR modelling efforts resulted in a number of useful models for the EuroMix project for a number of molecular pathway endpoints, including ER, AR, AhR and PPARgamma receptor binding and Aromatase Inhibition. These were implemented and are freely available in the online chemical modelling environment (OCHEM, <http://ochem.eu>). There are 3 available models for both ER-binding and AR-binding and one model each for Aromatase Enzyme Inhibition (relevant to predict compounds affecting steroidogenesis) and AhR and PPARgamma receptor binding (relevant for steatosis), see Table 2. Further details for the models are provided by Abdelaziz et al 2016.

Estrogen Receptor (ER)

In the first two ER binding models published by Amaziz, the library was screened for potential agonists at the estrogen receptor alpha using two different cell lines (ER-alpha-USA-bla GripTite™ cell line (ER-LBD) and BG1-Luc-4E2 cell line (ER-full)). The third model was developed using log ERBA data.

Androgen Receptor (AR)

In the first two AR-binding models published by Amaziz, the library was screened for potential agonists at the androgen receptor using two different cell lines (GeneBLAxer AR-UAS-bla-GripTite cell line (AR-LBD) and MDA-kb2 Ar-luc cell line (AR-full)). The third model was developed using log RP AR data.

Aromatase inhibition

Just one QSAR model was available for Aromatase inhibition, which used data from the MCF-7 aro ERE cell line (human breast carcinoma)

AhR

Just one QSAR model was available for AhR receptor agonists, which used data from the HepG2-AhR-Luc assay and HG2L7.5c1 cell line

PPAR-gamma

Just one QSAR model was available for PPAR gamma receptor agonists, which used data from the GeneBLazer PPAR gamma UAS-bla HEK293H cell line

Table 2. Details of the eight OCHEM models used in the EuroMix project to predict ER, AR, AhR and PPAR receptor binding.

Model	OCHEM Model Name	Data used to build model	Total number of unique compounds in training set
OCHEM ER model 1	Consensus Estrogen alpha agonists BG1 (published by Amaziz)	Estrogen receptor agonist, alpha BG1-Luc-4E2 cell line	6599 (826 active, 5910 inactive)
OCHEM ER model 2	Consensus estrogen receptor alpha agonists (published by Amaziz)	Estrogen receptor agonist, ER-alpha-USA-bla GripTite™ cell line (ER-LBD)	7425 (367 active, 7112 inactive)
OCHEM ER model 3	Estrogen receptor binding ASNN Model (published by Aveima)	Log ERBA data	743 (362 active, 381 inactive)
OCHEM AR model 1	Consensus Androgen agonists MDA (published by Amaziz)	Androgen receptor agonist, MDA-kb2 Ar-luc cell line (AR-full)	7760 (313 active, 7496 inactive)
OCHEM AR model 2	Consensus Androgen receptor agonists (published by Amaziz)	Androgen receptor agonist, GeneBLAzer AR-UAS-bla-GripTite cell line (AR-LBD)	7180 (242 active, 6956 inactive)
OCHEM AR model 3	Androgen receptor binding ASNN Model (published by Aveima)	Log RP_AR data (Jensen et al 2011)	744 (235 active, 509 inactive)
OCHEM Aromatase Inhibition model	Consensus aromatase inhibitors, qualitative (published by Amaziz)	Aromatase inhibition data, from the MCF-7 aro ERE cell line	6180 (329 active, 5877 inactive)
OCHEM AhR model	Consensus AhR activators (published by Amaziz)	AhR receptor agonists, HepG2-AhR-Luc assay, HG2L7.5c1 cell line	6988 (817 active, 6215 inactive)
OCHEM PPAR gamma model	Consensus agonists of PPARγ (published by Amaziz)	PPAR-gamma receptor agonist, GeneBLAzer PPAR gamma UAS-bla HEK293H cell line	6874 (204 active, 6684 inactive)

The OECD QSAR Toolbox (<http://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/theoecdqsartoolbox.htm>) is a software intended to be used by governments, the chemical industry and other stakeholders to fill gaps in (eco-) toxicity data needed for assessing the hazards of chemicals. The Toolbox incorporates information and tools from various sources into a logical workflow. Grouping chemicals into chemical categories is crucial to this workflow. The main features of the Toolbox are:

1. Identification of relevant structural characteristics and potential mechanism or mode of action of a target chemical.
2. Identification of other chemicals that have the same structural characteristics and/or mechanism or mode of action.
3. Use of existing experimental data to fill the data gap(s).

A number of profiling alerts / schemes were used in WP2 as described below:

OECD QSAR Toolbox DART scheme ER/AR alert

DART is a decision tree developed on the basis of the combination of known modes of action (MOA) and associated structural features, as well as an empirical association of structural fragments within molecules of reproductive or developmental toxic (DART) chemicals when MOA information was lacking. The decision tree was based on a review of 716 chemicals, most of which were positive, with only 16 negative. It is not designed to be used as a stand-alone tool but as part of weight of evidence.

OECD QSAR Toolbox ER-binding profiler

The ER-binding profiler classifies chemicals as non binders or binders depending on molecular weight (MW) and structural characteristics of the chemicals:

1. Very strong binders: Chemicals with MW between 200 and 500 Da and two rings with a hydroxyl group connected to each of them.
2. Strong binders: Chemicals with at least one 5- or 6-membered carbon ring with an unhindered hydroxyl or amino group and MW between 200 and 500 Da;
3. Moderate binders: Chemicals with at least one 5- or 6-membered carbon ring with an unhindered hydroxyl or amino group and MW between 170 and 200 Da;
4. Weak binders: Chemicals with at least one 5- or 6-membered carbon ring with an unhindered hydroxyl or amino group and MW less than 170 Da;

For the purposes of this phase of the project chemicals were classed as positive if they had any alert for ER-binding (weak, moderate, strong or very strong).

OECD QSAR Toolbox HESS alert

The HESS alert profiler was developed by National Institute of Technology and Evaluation (NITE), Japan. It contains category boundaries to be expected to induce similar toxicological effects in repeated dose oral toxicity. It was developed using repeated dose toxicity test data in the database of Hazard Evaluation Support System (HESS). Justification for each category (mechanistic or empirical information) is described.

OECD QSAR Toolbox rtER Expert system

rtER Expert System, USEPA. The Estrogen Receptor Expert System (ERES) Profiler is an effects-based automated system used to predict estrogen receptor binding affinity. Specially designed to prioritise pesticides (inert and antimicrobial) that do not include any steroidal structures and thus not capable of higher affinity ER interactions. The ERES is a logic rule-based decision tree that encodes the experts' mechanistic understanding with respect to both the chemical and biological aspects of the well-defined endpoint, or the ER bioassay domain.

PaDEL-DD Predictor

The PaDEL-DD Predictor model for hepatotoxicity is based on the paper of Liew et al 2011. The model predicts human hepatotoxicity based on 617 base models developed using PaDEL-descriptors on a large training set and a final consensus model based on stacked generalization with naive Bayes. It is a classification model and an applicability domain score is also provided as part of the output.

Pizzo structural alert

Nine structural alerts for liver toxicity were identified in the paper: Identification of structural alerts for liver and kidney toxicity using repeated dose toxicity data add (Pizzo et al 2015). The structural alerts were identified by the authors using Repeat-dose toxicity data from the hazard evaluation support system (HESS) database (Sakuratani et al 2013) and the ones presented were those giving the best percentage of true positives. In order to identify whether or not the EuroMix compounds contained the structural fragments giving rise to the alerts, the nine structures were added as 'custom profilers' in the OECD QSAR Toolbox.

The EuroMix chemicals were imported into the Toolbox as .sdf files and then the custom profilers were run under the Profiling tab of the Toolbox.

T.E.S.T. Developmental Toxicity model

Version 4.1. The Toxicity Estimation Software Tool is an open-source application developed by the US EPA. It estimates the toxicity of a compound by applying several QSAR methodologies thus allowing the user to have greater confidence in predicted toxicities. Among other toxicities it predicts developmental toxicity. The tool is freely downloadable from the EPA website (<http://www.epa.gov/nrmrl>).

The Toxicity Estimation Software Tool (T.E.S.T.) has been developed by the US EPA to allow users to easily estimate toxicity using a variety of QSAR methodologies described below, without requiring any external programs. Once a chemical has been entered using a range of format options, its toxicity can be estimated by several different advanced QSAR methodologies:

Hierarchical method: The toxicity for a given query compound is estimated using the weighted average of the predictions from several different models. The different models are obtained by using Ward's method to divide the training set into a series of structurally similar clusters. A genetic algorithm based technique is used to generate models for each cluster. The models are generated prior to runtime.

FDA method: The prediction for each test chemical is made using a new model that is fit to the chemicals that are most similar to the test compound. Each model is generated at runtime.

Single model method: Predictions are made using a multilinear regression model that is fit to the training set (using molecular descriptors as independent variables) using a genetic algorithm based approach. The regression model is generated prior to runtime.

Group contribution method: Predictions are made using a multilinear regression model that is fit to the training set (using molecular fragment counts as independent variables). The regression model is generated prior to runtime.

Nearest neighbor method: The predicted toxicity is estimated by taking an average of the 3 chemicals in the training set that are most similar to the test chemical.

Consensus method: The predicted toxicity is estimated by taking an average of the predicted toxicities from the above QSAR methods (provided the predictions are within the respective applicability domains).

In the validation procedure carried out by the developers the consensus method achieved the best results in terms of both prediction accuracy and prediction coverage, hence this was used to provide the estimates for the project.

VEGA models

The VEGA platform was developed by the Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche, “Mario Negri” in Milan and collaborators through a series of EU-funded projects. Models are available for a number of endpoints, including two models for Developmental Toxicity and one for Estrogen-receptor binding. The models generate transparent, reproducible and verifiable results, as required by regulators, and a comprehensive validation system is built in for all the models, which allows the user to assess the reliability of a prediction. The models are implemented inside the VEGA online platform, accessible at : <http://www.vega-qsar.eu>

VEGA Developmental Toxicity (Caesar model, v.2.1.7)

This QSAR classification model based on a Random Forest method, is implemented using WEKA open-source libraries. Full reference and details of the formulas can be found in the paper by Cassano et al 2010. It is based on a binary classification of FDA criteria (FDA categories A and B are considered as non toxicant, categories C, D and X are considered toxicant). The developmental toxicity data used to develop the model was extracted from the dataset of Arena et al 2004, and comprised subsets of information from the Teratogen Information System (TERIS) and US FDA guidelines (Briggs et al 1990, Shepard, 1992) and comprised teratogenicity data from both animal and human studies.

The applicability domain (AD) of predictions is assessed using an Applicability Domain Index (ADI) that has values from 0 (worst case) to 1 (best case). The ADI is calculated by grouping several other indices, each one taking into account a particular issue of the applicability domain. Most of the indices are based on the calculation of the most similar compounds found in the training and test set of the model, calculated by a similarity index that consider molecule's fingerprint and structural aspects (count of atoms, rings and relevant fragments). For each index, including the final ADI, three intervals for its values are defined, such that the first interval corresponds to a positive evaluation, the second one corresponds to a suspicious evaluation and the last one corresponds to a negative evaluation. Following, all applicability domain components are reported along with their explanation and the intervals used. The predictions are classed

as having either low reliability (compound out of the AD, moderate reliability (compound could be out of the AD, or high reliability (compound in the AD)

The model was built using a training set of 234 compounds and a test set of 58 compounds, with the following validation statistics:

- Training set: n = 234; Accuracy = 1.00; Specificity = 1.00; Sensitivity = 1.00
- Test set: n = 58; Accuracy = 0.84; Specificity = 0.59; Sensitivity = 0.95

VEGA Developmental Toxicity (PG library model, v. 1.0.0)

The model provides a qualitative prediction of developmental and reproductive toxicity, based on a virtual binary of possible toxicant compounds. The model implements a virtual library of toxicant compounds as described in the study from Procter & Gamble (Shengde et al 2013). In this study a 25 categories of possible toxicant were identified, and for each category an extended list of virtual compounds was generated. The model implements these categories, and tries to find an exact match between the given compound and any of the virtual compounds in the library. If a match is found, a prediction of “Toxicant” is given, otherwise a “NON Toxicant” prediction is provided. Further details of the categories used can be found at : <http://www.vega-qsar.eu>).

The original dataset used in the cited work, consisting of 641 compounds, was implemented as the training set. An Applicability domain assessment, as described above is part of the output. The following, statistics were obtained applying the model to its original dataset:

- Training set: n = 641; Accuracy = 0.82; Specificity = 0.44; Sensitivity = 0.85

VEGA RBA model, v. 1.0.1

The model provides a qualitative prediction for Relative Binding Affinity (RBA) for endocrine disruptor screening. This model is developed from a large heterogeneous database of ER RBA results (Japanese METI database, Meti, 2002). It contains experimentally determined values of human ER alpha for both receptor binding (RBA) and reporter gene (RA) assays, expressed as percentage of activity using 17-estradiol as reference. To develop the model, any detectable activity was labelled active and no detectable activity was labelled inactive. This QSAR classification model is based on a classification and regression tree (CART) algorithm using a training set of 806 compounds as described by Roncaglioni et al 2008. An Applicability domain assessment, as described above is part of the output.

The model was built using a training set of 656 compounds and a test set of 150 compounds, with the following validation statistics:

- Training set: n = 656; Accuracy = 0.86; Specificity = 0.85; Sensitivity = 0.87
- Test set: n = 150; Accuracy = 0.84; Specificity = 0.88; Sensitivity = 0.78

Validation

To compare the individual model and “weight of evidence” model performance, a dataset of compounds with experimental data for each of the three endpoints was identified in order to provide an external validation using the same validation set used for all the models for that particular endpoint. The two-dimensional structures of the validation compounds were obtained as described previously for the chemical inventory compounds. These compounds were then run through the range of models applicable to that particular endpoint. The validity of the predictions was investigated by calculating the so-called Cooper Statistics (Cooper et al 1979) below:

Sensitivity (true positive rate) = $TP/TP+FN$

Specificity (True negative rate) = $TN/TN+FP$

Accuracy = $(TN+TP)/(TN+FP+FN+TP)$

where TP = true positive, TN = true negative, FP = false positive and FN = false negative

Hepatotoxicity validation set

The dataset of 218 compounds with liver toxicity data described by Pizzo et al 2015 was obtained from the authors. This dataset was obtained by the authors by pruning Repeated-dose toxicity (RDT) data present in the Hazard Evaluation Support System (HESS) database (HESS 2013) downloaded from the OECD QSAR Toolbox (<http://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/theoecdqsartoolbox.htm>). This database provides NOAEL and LOAEL values and gives information on the organ toxicity for 503 chemicals tested on rats by oral exposure over periods ranging from 28 to 120 days. For the selection of the liver toxicity dataset the authors considered the compounds for which LOAEL related to effects on liver was reported and they labelled them as “active” substances. Those compounds with reported LOAEL effects on organs other than liver were considered negative controls and were labelled as “inactive”. The liver dataset contains 218 compounds of which 121 were active and 97 were inactive.

Developmental Toxicity validation set

The external test set from the USA EPA’s T.E.S.T. developmental toxicity QSAR model was used to validate the developmental toxicity models used in the EuroMix project. The dataset was downloaded from the US EPA’s website (<https://www.epa.gov/chemical-research/toxicity-estimation-software-tool-test>). The dataset contains 58 compounds with developmental toxicity data of which 41 are active and 17 inactive.

Endocrine Activity validation set

For ER-binding

The external test set from the VEGA RBA QSAR model was used to validate the ER-binding Endocrine activity models used in the EuroMix project. This test set from a large heterogeneous database of ER RBA results (Japanese METI database, Meti, 2002) contains experimentally determined values of human ER alpha for both receptor binding (RBA) and reporter gene (RA) assays, expressed as percentage of activity using 17-estradiol as reference. Compounds were labelled active where there was any detectable activity labelled inactive where there was no detectable activity. The dataset containing agonists and antagonists, was downloaded and contains qualitative RBA data for 150 compounds of which 54 were classed as active and 96 classed as inactive.

For AR-binding

The external test set of Androgen antagonists from the OCHEM Log RP_AR model published by Aveima on the OCHEM Web pages (<https://ochem.eu>) was used to validate the AR-binding Endocrine activity models used in the EuroMix project . The data for this model consisted of the inhibitory concentration for 25% or 50% of the response induced by the synthetic androgen metribolone (R1881) in harvested Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) cells (Rybacka et al 2015), as collected by Jensen et al. (2011). The dataset was downloaded from the OCHEM Web pages as an .sdf file and contains 186 compounds with binary log RP AR data of which 58 are active and 128 are inactive.

Weight of evidence approach

There is no definitive method for devising a weight of evidence from a number of different *in silico* predictions. The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) recommends the combination of reliability, relevance and adequacy, when proposing a weight of evidence argument from different types of evidence, including *in silico* results (ECHA 2010). Specifically for (Q)SAR data the US FDA offers a pragmatic approach to weight of evidence using the results from a number of (Q)SAR methods (Matthews 2009). Price et al 2014 used a modified form of this majority voting approach to predict the carcinogenicity and mutagenicity of chemical migrants from food packaging.

As a first stage to assign compounds to a CAG level 1 membership (Toxicant, Non Toxicant), a similar simple majority voting approach using the results from the suite of (Q)SAR models available for the particular endpoint was employed. The results (including those which are equivocal or of low reliability) from all of the models applicable for a particular endpoint were considered. A “Positive” prediction was assigned if half or more of the models gave a Positive or Equivocal prediction and a “Negative” prediction was assigned if half or more of the models gave a Negative prediction.

For both the hepatotoxicity and ER-binding endpoints, where the results from 10 models were considered, a “Positive” prediction was thus made if 5 or more models gave a Positive or Equivocal prediction. For both the Developmental toxicity and AR-binding endpoints, the results from 4 models were considered and so a “Positive” prediction was thus made if 2 or more models gave a Positive or Equivocal prediction. For the Endocrine endpoint a “Positive” prediction was made if a “Positive” prediction was made for either ER or AR receptor binding.

Further work will be carried to develop a more refined decision scheme to take into account the strengths and weaknesses of the underlying models and reliability of the results, using Bayesian statistics. This will also give a chemical specific prediction of CAG membership with an associated uncertainty which can directly be used in a probabilistic way to link in with the probabilistic treatment of the exposure data. The development of a more refined decision scheme using Bayesian statistics will be the focus of D2.4 in WP2.

Refinement of CAGs

Further information obtained from a number of the (Q)SAR models is useful output to further refine CAG membership, details of which are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Model output potentially useful for refinement (sub-categorisation) of CAGs.

Model	Endpoint	Description of model output
COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model	Hepatotoxicity, Endocrine	Identifies which receptors the compound may be a ligand for the following receptors related to steatosis : AR, AhR, ER, PPAR, PR and RXR
COSMOS LXR-binding QSAR models	Hepatotoxicity	Any compounds giving a positive prediction to these LXR-binding QSAR models may cause steatosis
DEREK	Hepatotoxicity, Developmental	Detailed information on the effects and sometimes mechanisms of action for known toxicants with the same substructure causing the

Model	Endpoint	Description of model output
	Toxicity, Endocrine	alert are provided. Alerts relating to steatosis, teratogenicity and receptor binding will be identified
Multicase	Hepatotoxicity	Which of the 6 modules give positive prediction (acute liver damage, liver function tests, bile duct disorders, Cholestasis, jaundice and gall bladder disorders)
OCHEM models	Hepatotoxicity, Endocrine	Nuclear receptor binding models specific for a particular receptor (AhR, AR, ER, PPARgamma)
OECD QSAR Toolbox DART scheme	Developmental Toxicity, Endocrine	Chemical class giving rise to Developmental toxicity or ER-binding alert and mechanism of action where available
OECD Toolbox ER-binding profiler	Endocrine	Provides details of whether positive compounds are weak, moderate, strong or very strong binders to ER receptor and whether –OH and/or –NH2 group implicated
OECD QSAR Toolbox HESS alert	Hepatotoxicity	Chemical class giving rise to Hepatotoxicity alert
OECD Toolbox rtER Expert profiler	Endocrine	Provides chemical class giving rise to ER-binding alert
Pizzo alert	Hepatotoxicity	Mechanisms of action available for some of the structural alerts. None are specific for steatosis
VEGA PG library model	Developmental Toxicity	Chemical class giving rise to Developmental toxicity alert

3D-receptor molecular docking

Molecular Modeling

The crystallographic structures of the ligand binding domain (LBD) of human endogenous hormone receptors (human androgen receptor, hAR, human estrogen receptor alpha, hER- α , human estrogen receptor beta, hER- β , and human progesterone receptor, hPR) were downloaded from the RCSB Protein Data Bank [PDB entry: 1ZUC , hPR; 2AM9 hAR; 3UUD hER- α ; 3OLS hER- β , respectively] and carefully

inspected. A preparation protocol implemented in the MOE Suite was applied to their 3D macromolecular structures, in order to correct potential gaps derived from experimental determination, to relax interatomic bumps produced by hydrogen atom addition, to refine protein arrangement and to optimize energy. Energy minimization (EM) was performed using the Amber10:EHT force field and the reaction field solvation model, up to a RMS gradient of 0.0001 kcal/(mol Å²). All the computational procedures were carried out with the Molecular Operating Environment (MOE).

Binding site analysis

The binding site of each receptor was identified through the MOE Site Finder program, which uses a geometric approach to calculate putative binding sites in a protein, starting from its 3D structure. This method is not based on energy models, but uses alpha spheres, which are a generalization of convex hulls. The binding sites predicted *in silico* were in agreement with the pockets experimentally identified by the ligands co-crystallized with the investigated proteins.

Molecular docking

The *in silico* screening of investigated chemicals was carried out with the Dock program implemented in the MOE Simulation module following the procedure described in Eberini et al., *J Comput Aided Mol Des*, 2011, 25(8):743-52. During the placement procedure, the whole structures of hAR, hER- α , hER- β , hPR LBD were set as receptor, the co-crystallized ligands were set as binding site and the optimized structure of each compound in the database was selected as ligand. For each ligand, 3D conformers were generated by applying a collection of preferred torsion angles to the rotatable bonds, while changes of bond lengths, bond angles and ring bending were not allowed. The selected placement methodology was Triangle Matcher, in which the poses are generated by superposing triplets of ligand atoms and triplets of receptor site point. The receptor site points are alpha spheres centres over co-crystallized ligand and represent locations of tight packing. Poses were scored according to London dG scoring, which estimates the free energy of binding of the ligand from a given pose.

Only the top scoring solution for each compound was kept and submitted to a refinement step, fixing all receptor atoms and using the GBVI/WSA dG scoring function to evaluate the final binding free energy. Also for this step, only one pose for each compound was kept, obtaining a sorted list of free energy values. Binding free energy values obtained for natural ligands of each receptor were used as threshold to discriminate potentially active chemicals.

Construction of in silico toxicity predictions database

The results from all of the individual models and also the “Positive” or “Negative” scores, presented as 1 and 0 respectively, were collated and recorded in a database, i.e. the ***In Silico Toxicity Prediction Database, which is placed at the EuroMix Share(WP02 QSAR TTC.*** A majority Consensus score was also calculated for the different endpoints.

A final quality check of the results in the database was carried out to ensure that no errors had been introduced by working from different Chemical Inventories and combining and copying and pasting information. A random 5 % of the compounds from each chemical type were run individually as .mol files, or using the SMILES code as applicable, through all of the in silico models. The results were recorded in a table and then checked against the results in the database. The numbers of models for each endpoint with a “Positive” prediction were then added together, a Consensus Score calculated and checked with the entry in the database.

Results

Hepatotoxicity models

In total ten models were run for the EuroMix compounds and the validation set. In order to evaluate model performance the so called Cooper statistics (Cooper et al 1979) were calculated for all of the models using the validation set. For the COSMOS LXR-binding QSAR model using PADEL descriptors, the sensitivity was almost zero, so it is possible this model is not properly implemented on the COSMOS WebPortal. The results of this model were thus not considered further. A simple majority weight of evidence score (where a result is classed positive if half or more of the models give a positive result) was also calculated, and the results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Cooper statistics for Hepatotoxicity models

Model	Sensitivity (True positive rate: TP/TP+FN)	Specificity (True negative rate: TN/TN+FP)	Accuracy (TN+TP)/(TN+FP+FN+TP)
COSMOS LXR-binding QSAR model (PADEL descriptors) ^a	0.03	0.98	0.45
COSMOS LXR-binding QSAR model (RDKit descriptors)	0.69	0.48	0.60
COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model	0.31	0.80	0.53
DEREK Nexus (equivocal and above positive)	0.45	0.60	0.52
Fera QSAR model using CDK descriptors	0.85	0.24	0.58
MULTICASE Highest Consensus model (no call and out of domain classed as positive)	0.72	0.31	0.54
OCHEM AhR binding model	0.29	0.85	0.54
OCHEM PPARgamma model	0.30	0.86	0.55
OECD QSAR Toolbox HESS alerts	0.37	0.72	0.53
PaDEL-DD Predictor	0.78	0.16	0.50

Pizzo structural alert	0.46	0.90	0.66
Majority Consensus using 10 models -Positive if 5 or more models positive	0.63	0.64	0.64

^a – as the sensitivity was so low for this model, the results were not further considered in the project.

The predictions statistics using the majority weight of evidence approach provides a reasonable result with an accuracy of 0.64 and a balanced sensitivity/ specificity. This approach was thus considered suitable to provide an initial simple consensus prediction for all of the EuroMix compounds. The results of the *in silico* predictions for all of the EuroMix compounds are available in a database (***In Silico Toxicity Prediction Database, EuroMix Share/WP02 QSAR TTC***). Numbers of compounds predicted to be positive/negative for the three endpoints, according to the chemical type, are shown in Table 8.

Developmental Toxicity Endpoint

In total 5 models were run for the EuroMix compounds and the validation set. In order to evaluate model performance the so called Cooper statistics (Cooper et al 1979) were calculated for all of the models using the validation set. The Toolbox DART alerts are based on the same PG dataset used to develop the VEGA PG library model and as can be seen from Table 5, the performance of the two models was very similar. As the VEGA model also provides a measure of the reliability of the prediction for a particular compound, including applicability domain scores, then this model was used in the Weight of Evidence approach. Although the accuracy of the Derek Nexus predictions was only around 0.5, the specificity was high, so minimising false negatives, and so the predictions were used in this exercise. The output from Derek Nexus can also provide information useful for higher level CAG assignment. A simple majority weight of evidence score (where a result is classed positive if half or more of the models give a positive result) was also calculated. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Cooper statistics for Developmental toxicity models

Model	Sensitivity (True positive rate: TP/TP+FN)	Specificity (True negative rate: TN/TN+FP)	Accuracy (TN+TP)/(TN+FP+FN+TP)
DEREK Nexus	0.32	0.82	0.47

Model	Sensitivity (True positive rate: TP/TP+FN)	Specificity (True negative rate: TN/TN+FP)	Accuracy (TN+TP)/(TN+FP+FN+TP)
(equivocal and above positive)			
Toolbox DART alert ^a	0.73	0.71	0.72
T.E.S.T	0.90	0.53	0.79
VEGA (Caesar model)	0.95	0.59	0.84
VEGA (PG library model)	0.73	0.76	0.74
Majority Consensus using 4 models -Positive if 2 or more models positive	0.93	0.65	0.84

^a – model based on same data as the VEGA PG library model so not considered in the Weight of Evidence

The predictions statistics using the majority weight of evidence approach provides a good result with an accuracy of 0.84. This approach was thus used to provide a consensus prediction for all of the EuroMix compounds. The results of the *in silico* predictions for all of the EuroMix compounds are available in a database (*In Silico Toxicity Prediction Database, Euromix share/WP02 QSAR TTC*). Numbers of compounds predicted to be positive/negative for the three endpoints, according to the chemical type, are shown in Table 8.

Endocrine Active Substances Endpoint

A number of *in silico* models were available for Estrogen Receptor (ER) and Androgen Receptor (AR) binding. Some of the models covered both ER and AR binding, whereas some were specific to one receptor only. Estimates of whether the chemicals were likely to be ER and AR receptor binders were determined separately using the relevant models shown in Tables 6 and 7. Potential endocrine activity was predicted if ER and/or AR binding was predicted. If neither ER nor AR binding was predicted from the weight of evidence consensus then the chemical was deemed to be inactive for Endocrine Activity.

ER-binding models

In total 10 ER-binding models were run for the EuroMix compounds and the validation set. In order to evaluate model performance the so called Cooper statistics (Cooper et al 1979) were calculated for all of the models using the validation set. A simple majority weight of evidence score (where a result is classed positive if half or more of the models give a positive result) was also calculated. The results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Cooper statistics for ER –binding Endocrine Activity models

Model	Sensitivity (True positive rate: TP/TP+FN)	Specificity (True negative rate: TN/TN+FP)	Accuracy (TN+TP)/(TN+FP+FN+TP)
COSMOS Nuclear receptor model (ER receptor)	0.81	0.40	0.55
DEREK (equivocal and above positive)	0.31	0.98	0.74
Fera c45 Model	0.69	0.86	0.80
OCHEM ER-binding model 1	0.87	0.47	0.61
OCHEM ER-binding model 2	0.83	0.67	0.73
OCHEM ER-binding model 3	0.94	0.96	0.95
OECD QSAR Toolbox DART scheme ER/AR alert	0.28	0.83	0.63
OECD QSAR Toolbox ER-binding profiler	0.63	0.73	0.69
OECD QSAR Toolbox rtER Expert system profiler	0.26	0.84	0.63
VEGA RBA model	0.78	0.88	0.84
Majority Consensus using 10 models -Positive if 5 or more models positive	0.80	0.87	0.84

The predictions statistics using the majority weight of evidence approach provides a good result with an accuracy of 0.84. This approach was thus used to provide a consensus prediction for all of the EuroMix compounds. The results of the *in silico* predictions for all of the EuroMix compounds are available in a database (*In Silico Toxicity Prediction Database, Euromix share/WP02 QSAR TTC*). Numbers of compounds predicted to be positive/negative for the three endpoints, according to the chemical type, are shown in Table 8.

AR-binding models

In total 4 AR-binding models were run for the EuroMix compounds and the validation set. In order to evaluate model performance the so called Cooper statistics (Cooper et al 1979) were calculated for all of the models using the validation set. A simple majority weight of evidence score (where a result is classed positive if half or more of the models give a positive result) was also calculated. The results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Cooper statistics for AR –binding Endocrine Activity models

Model	Sensitivity (True positive rate: TP/TP+FN)	Specificity (True negative rate: TN/TN+FP)	Accuracy (TN+TP)/(TN+FP+FN+TP)
COSMOS Nuclear receptor model	0.53	0.86	0.76
OCHEM AR-binding model 1	0.22	0.88	0.68
OCHEM AR-binding model 2	0.21	0.91	0.69
OCHEM AR-binding model 3	0.74	0.88	0.83
Majority Consensus using 4 models -Positive if 2 or more models positive	0.57	0.88	0.78

The predictions statistics using the majority weight of evidence approach provides a good result with an accuracy of 0.78. This approach was thus used to provide a consensus prediction for all of the EuroMix compounds. The results of the *in silico* predictions for all of the EuroMix compounds are available in a database (*In Silico Toxicity Prediction Database, Euromix share/WP02 QSAR TTC*). Numbers of compounds predicted to be positive/negative for the three endpoints, according to the chemical type, are shown in Table 8.

Predictions for EuroMix compounds

The results of the *in silico* predictions for all of the EuroMix compounds and for the three endpoints of interest to the project, are available in a database (*In Silico Toxicity Prediction Database, Euromix share/WP02 QSAR TTC*). An overview of the numbers of compounds predicted to be positive, by chemical type is shown in Table 8.

Table 8 Majority Consensus predictions summary data for EuroMix compounds according to chemical type

Chemical Type	Hepatotoxicity	Developmental Toxicity	Endocrine Activity (ER and/or AR)
PPP	63% positive (299/477)	70% positive (336/477)	17% positive (80/477) ER: 2% positive (10/477) AR: 16% positive (76/477)
Biocide	64% positive (18/28)	71% positive (20/28)	21% positive (6/28) ER: 7% positive (2/28) AR: 21% positive (6/28)
NIAS_FCM	33% positive (20/60)	58% positive (35/60)	20% positive (12/60) ER: 12% positive (7/60) AR: 10% positive (6/60)
Mycotoxins	55% positive (11/20)	80% positive (16/20)	45% positive (9/20) ER: 15% positive (3/20) AR: 40% positive (8/20)
Alkaloids	58% positive (23/40)	95% positive (38/40)	0% positive (0/40) ER: 0% positive (0/40) AR: 0% positive (0/40)
Env Poll	100% positive (213/213)	8% positive (17/213)	24% positive (51/213) ER: 23% positive (49/213) AR: 1% positive (2/213)
Other	48% positive (99/207)	70% positive (145/207)	35% positive (73/207) ER: 21% positive (43/207) AR: 25% positive (52/207)

3-D molecular docking results

For a certain number of chemicals, lower binding free energy values were found compared to those of reference compounds, suggesting that these compounds may bind to each selected receptor with a higher affinity than natural ligands. In detail, the number of chemicals with higher affinity than reference compounds, for each respective receptor are: hAR – 2; hER- α – 29; hER- β – 58; hPR – 20. In tables 9–12, the binding free energy values and the chemical class of the 20 top-scoring chemicals for each receptor are reported. Compounds marked with “**” recur among the top-scoring list in two or more different receptors; natural ligands are marked in bold.

Table 9: hAR top scoring chemicals

Compounds	Chemical classes	Binding free energy (kcal/mol)
Endosulfan **	PPP	-9.6
Heptachlor **	PPP	-9.3
Dihydrotestosterone	Natural ligand	-9.2

Table 10: hER- α top scoring chemicals

Compounds	Chemical classes	Binding free energy (kcal/mol)
Endrin **	PPP	-10.1
2-[2-(4-Nonylphenoxy)ethoxy]ethanol **	Other	-9.2
Dihexyl phthalate	NIAS_FCM	-9.0
Oxasulfuron **	PPP	-8.8
Labetalol hydrochloride **	Other	-8.4
Dicyclohexyl phthalate	Other	-8.4
Azoxystrobin	PPP	-8.4
Primisulfuron-methyl	PPP	-8.4
2-(4-nonylphenoxy)acetic acid	Other	-8.4
Dipentyl Phthalate **	Other	-8.3
Ethametsulfuron methyl	PPP	-8.3

Carfentrazone-ethyl **	PPP	-8.3
Enalapril maleate	Other	-8.3
Thiodicarb **	PPP	-8.3
Allethrin (D-cis,trans-Allethrin) **	PPP	-8.3
Flazasulfuron **	PPP	-8.3
Beflubutamid **	PPP	-8.3
Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane **	Other	-8.3
Benalaxyl **	PPP	-8.3
Propoxycarbazone-sodium	PPP	-8.3
...
17beta-estradiol	Natural ligand	-8.1

Table 11: hER- β top scoring chemicals

Compounds	Chemical classes	Binding free energy (kcal/mol)
Endosulfan **	PPP	-9.9
Endrin **	PPP	-8.9
2-[2-(4-Nonylphenoxy)ethoxy]ethanol **	Other	-8.6
Heptachlor **	PPP	-8.5
Imazosulfuron **	PPP	-8.5
Tetramethrin	PPP	-8.4
Lactofen **	PPP	-8.4
AGN191701	Other	-8.4
Butyl benzyl phthalate	NIAS_FCM	-8.3
Flucarbazone-sodium	PPP	-8.3
Labetalol hydrochloride **	Other	-8.3
Ethion **	PPP	-8.3
Volinanserin	Other	-8.3
Beflubutamid **	PPP	-8.2
Tepaloxymid	PPP	-8.2

Thiodicarb **	PPP	-8.2
8-prenylnaringenin (8-PN)	Other	-8.2
Allethrin (D-cis,trans-Allethrin) **	PPP	-8.1
Dipentyl Phthalate **	Other	-8.1
Spirodiclofen	PPP	-8.1
...
17beta-estradiol	Natural ligand	-7.7

Table 12: hPR top scoring chemicals

Compounds	Chemical classes	Binding free energy (kcal/mol)
Endosulfan **	PPP	-10.1
Heptachlor **	PPP	-10.1
Triasulfuron	PPP	-8.9
Imazosulfuron **	PPP	-8.6
Propoxycarbazone-sodium	PPP	-8.5
Lactofen **	PPP	-8.4
Ethion **	PPP	-8.4
Fluazinam	PPP	-8.4
Propargite	PPP	-8.3
Halofenozide	PPP	-8.3
Metrafenone	PPP	-8.3
Cyflufenamid	PPP	-8.2
Flumetralin	PPP	-8.2
Labetalol hydrochloride **	Other	-8.2
Bensulfuron methyl	PPP	-8.2
Allethrin (D-cis,trans-Allethrin) **	PPP	-8.2
Fenpyrazamine	PPP	-8.1
Bupirimate	PPP	-8.1

Cloquintocet-mexyl	PPP	-8.1
Flufenacet	PPP	-8.1
Progesterone	Natural ligand	-8.1

Full details of the binding energies for all the EuroMix compounds are shown in the database (*In Silico Toxicity Prediction Database, EuroMix Share/WP02 QSAR TTC*).

Refinement of CAGs

As an example of refinement of CAGs using detailed model output, the hepatotoxicity endpoint CAG level 1 membership was further refined by identifying those potential hepatotoxicants for which there was evidence for steatosis. If the majority of the following model outputs were positive for a compound then the compound was considered to have the potential to cause steatosis (CAG level 2):

- Derek hepatotoxicity alerts specific to steatosis (See Annex 4)
- Hepatosteatois alert from the COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model
- Positive in the COSMOS LXR-binding QSAR model
- Positive results from the OCHEM AhR gamma receptor binding models
- Positive results from the OCHEM PPAR gamma receptor binding models

The Nuclear Receptor models also allowed refinement to CAG levels 3 and 4. The results of the steatosis refinement are shown in the database (*In Silico Toxicity Prediction Database, EuroMix Share/WP02 QSAR TTC*). An overview of the numbers of compounds predicted to cause steatosis, split by chemical type, is shown in Table 13. The evidence indicates that for all chemical types other than the Alkaloids, steatosis may be caused for a reasonable proportion of compounds predicted to be hepatotoxic. Although 58 % of the Alkaloids were predicted to be hepatotoxic, using the Weight of Evidence Consensus, none of the Alkaloids were predicted to cause steatosis.

Table 13. Percentage and numbers of compounds classed as hepatotoxicants (CAG level 1) and those with potential to cause Steatosis (CAG level 2), where the majority of models specific for steatosis are positive (illustrated when either 3 or 4 of the 5 models are positive)

Chemical Type	Predicted to be Hepatotoxic	Evidence for Steatosis (at least 3 of 5 models positive)	Evidence for Steatosis (at least 4 of 5 models positive)
PPP	63% positive (299/477)	47 % positive (224/477)	22% positive (104/477)
Biocide	64% positive (18/28)	57 % positive (16/28)	39% positive (11/28)
NIAS_FCM	33% positive (20/60)	15% positive (9/60)	5% positive (3/60)
Mycotoxins	55% positive (11/20)	45% positive (9/20)	35% positive (7/20)
Alkaloids	58% positive (23/40)	0% positive (0/40)	0% positive (0/40)
Env Poll	100% positive (213/213)	95% positive (202/213)	62% positive (131/213)
Other	48% positive (99/207)	32% positive (66/207)	12% positive (24/207)

Summary

The aim of task 2.2 was to attempt to establish a set of *in silico* procedures that would enable prediction of the endpoints of interest (CAG level 1: hepatotoxicity, developmental toxicity and endocrine disruption) where experimental data is not available and further to refine the toxicants CAG with additional

information from the models e.g. phenomenological effect (CAG level 2) mode of action/mechanism of action (CAG levels 3 and 4).

A number of different *in silico* models were identified to predict the toxicity of compounds for three endpoints. These models were either freely available, or were available with license to EuroMix project partners. The methods used in the project included a combination of predictive computational models based on Structure Activity Relationships (SAR), Quantitative Structure Activity Relationships (QSAR), expert systems and 3D molecular docking with key receptors. Some models predict the endpoints of interest at CAG level 1: e.g. hepatotoxicity, developmental toxicity, whilst others are more specific and predict binding to key receptors e.g. ER, AR, LXR receptor binding.

The CAS numbers / names of the chemicals from the list produced in task 2.1 was used to download the 2D chemical structures from the freely available on-line chemical databases ChemIDPlus, Pubchem or Chempider. A few compounds were not suitable for (Q)SAR models, e.g. inorganics, metal complexes or mixtures and these were not considered. Furthermore any salts present were converted to the parent structure to enable them to be run through the (Q)SAR models. For molecular docking optimised 3D structures were generated and used.

The test compounds were run through the available suite of *in silico* models and a “weight of evidence” (WoE) approach was taken, generate a Consensus prediction. As a primary screen, to determine CAG level 1 membership, a simple majority voting scheme was used, where if at least half of the models gave a positive prediction the Consensus prediction was “Positive”. The results of the individual models and Consensus prediction are provided in an *in silico* toxicity prediction database (***In Silico* Toxicity Prediction Database, EuroMix Share/WP02 QSAR TTC**).

The performance of the individual models, as well as the Consensus prediction, was validated using test sets of compounds with known experimental activity (both positive and negative) for the endpoint in question. This enabled the accuracy of the models and numbers of false positives and false negatives to be determined. Very few individual models showed a high accuracy, and for some the balance between Sensitivity (true positive rate) and Specificity (true negative rate) was skewed. However, the predictions statistics using the majority WoE Consensus results provides a reasonable result for the hepatotoxicity endpoint (Accuracy of 0.64) and good performance for the other endpoints, with Accuracies of 0.84, 0.78 and 0.84 ER–receptor binding, AR-receptor binding and Developmental toxicity respectively.

The results of the (Q)SAR models provide CAG membership, however they do not give a quantitative prediction of the potency of a chemical. In task 2.3 for a first tier potency estimate other methodology will be applied (literature data, read across, TTC concept). The molecular docking analyses are a promising tool

as they provide quantitative results, and potency factors may be derived based on the binding energy of a molecule to the receptor.

In task 2.2 a simple majority Consensus prediction generated using the results from the suite of *in silico* models was used as a first step. However, this decision scheme does not take into account the strengths and weaknesses of the underlying models. The uncertainty analyses of the final EuroMix approach should include the sensitivity/specificity/accuracy rate of the individual (Q)SAR method used. The next stage of the project, to be carried under task 2.4, will be to use the selected *in silico* models in a more refined decision scheme, based on Bayesian statistics. This would address both issues of taking into account strengths and weaknesses of individual models, and also give a chemical specific prediction of CAG membership with an associated uncertainty which can directly be used in a probabilistic way. This allows the “retain and refine” principle where in principle every chemical in the mixture is used for risk assessment, but the probability that a single substance will contribute significantly to the risk is different (very low for some substance, higher for others). It also combines well with the probabilistic treatment of the exposure data, giving a probability for combined exposure. The development of a more refined decision scheme using Bayesian statistics will be the focus of D2.4 in WP2.

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Annex 1 Details of chemicals from the Chemical Inventory which were removed, modified to make suitable for QSAR analysis or which were downloaded from sources other than ChemIDPlus

Table A1. PPPs (A/A numbers refer to latest version of Chemical Inventory at the time of writing 5 9 2016)

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
8	Abamectin	71751-41-2	Mixture of 2 compounds, not suitable in silico	Removed
15	alpha - Cypermethrin	67375-30-8	Stereoisomer of A/A 69 so duplicate	Removed – used results from A/A 69
16	Aluminium phosphide	20859-73-8	Metal complex, not suitable in silico	Removed
32	Bispyribac-sodium	125401-92-5	Sodium salt	Keep, but convert to neutral parent compound
50	chlormequat - chloride	999-81-5	If remove Cl- to make suitable for in silico then is duplicate of A/A 49 Chlormequat	Removed – used results from A/A 49
57	Clethodim	99129-21-2	Isomer represented by Pubchem and ChemSpider used	Selected most representative structural isomer
62	Clothianidin	210880-92-5	MW corrected and isomer represented by Pubchem and ChemSpider used	Selected most representative structural isomer
63	Copper compounds	n/a	Not suitable in silico	Removed
64	Cycloxydim	101205-02-1	Selected structural isomer most prominent (ChemIDPlus and Chemispider one)	Selected most representative structural isomer
65	Cyflufenamid	180409-60-3	Selected structural isomer most prominent (ChemIDPlus and Chemispider one)	Selected most representative structural isomer
96	Dodine	112-65-2	CAS should be 112-65-2. Selected structural isomer most prominent (ChemIDPlus and	CAS 112-65-2 Selected most representative structural isomer

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
			Chemispider one)	
97	Emamectin Benzoate	155569-91-8	Benzoate salt	Keep, but used parent structure without benzoate
111	Fenbutatin oxide	13356-08-6	Tin complex, not suitable for in silico	Removed
131	Flupyrsulfuron-methyl (DPX KE 459)	144740-54-5	Na salt, convert to parent	Keep, but used parent structure
141	Fosetyl	39148-24-8	Al 3+ salt, use parent monoethyl phosphonate (CAS 15845-66-6)	Keep, but used parent structure
145	Gibberellin	173269-32-4	CAS not recognised (ChemIDPlus, Pubchem or ChemSpider). There are a number of gibberellins (A4, A12, GA19, GA28) – don't know which one so exclude	Removed
156	Imidacloprid	138261-41-3	Isomer represented by Pubchem and ChemSpider used	Selected most representative structural isomer
158	iodosulfuron methyl sodium	144550-36-7	Na salt, convert to parent	Keep, but used parent structure
165	lambda-Cyhalothrin	91465-08-6	Isomer of A/A 143 so duplicate	Removed, but used results from A/A 143
169	Magnesium phosphide	12057-74-8	Not suitable in silico	Removed
171	Maltodextrin	9050-36-6	Structure unspecified	Removed
178	Metalaxyl-M	70630-17-0	Stereoisomer of A/A 177 so duplicate	Removed, but used results from A/A 177
180	Metam sodium)	144-54-7	Na salt, use parent	Keep, but used parent structure
213	Prohexadione - Calcium	127277-53-6	Calcium salt not suitable for in silico, used parent	Keep, but used parent structure
222	Prothioconazole	178928-70-6	Isomer represented by Pubchem and	Selected most representative

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
			ChemSpider used	structural isomer
244	Spinetoram	187166-15-0	Mixture, not suitable	Removed
245	Spinosad	168316-95-8	Mixture, not suitable	Removed
252	Sulfur	7704-34-9	Not suitable in silico	Removed
272	Tralkoxydim	87820-88-0	Selected structural isomer most prominent (ChemIDPlus and ChemSpider one)	Selected most representative structural isomer
276	Triazoxide	72459-58-6	Isomer represented by Pubchem and ChemSpider used	Selected most representative structural isomer
287	zeta-Cypermethrin	1315501-18-8	Isomer of cypermethrin so duplicate (keep 52315-07-8) A/A 69	Removed, but used results from A/A 69
288	Ziram	137-30-4	Metal complex, not suitable in silico	Removed
303	Oxytetracycline hydrochloride	2058-46-0	Removed HCl salt	Keep, but used parent structure (CAS 79-57-2)
326	Dinocap	39300-45-3	Chemidplus and Pubchem structure is broken down into components	Downloaded structure from ChemSpider
328	Maneb	12427-38-2	Metal complex so not suitable for QSARs	Removed
329	Metiram	9006-42-2	Metal complex so not suitable for QSARs (if removed metal duplicate of A/A 398)	Removed, but used results from A/A 398
330	Propineb	12071-83-9	Metal complex so not suitable for QSARs	Removed
332	S-Metolachlor	87392-12-9	Stereoisomer, duplicate of AA 461	Removed but used results from A/A461
341	2,4-D, diethanolamine salt	5742-19-8	Salt not suitable for QSAR. If remove salt then is duplicate	Removed but used results from A/A 4
342	2,4-D, dimethylamine salt	2008-39-1	Salt not suitable for QSAR. If remove salt	Removed but used results from

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
			then is duplicate	A/A 4
343	2,4-D, isopropylamine salt	5742-17-6	Salt not suitable for QSAR. If remove salt then is duplicate	Removed but used results from A/A 4
349	3,5,7-Triaza-1-azoniatricyclo(3.3.1.1 ^{superscript3,7})decane, 1-methyl-, chloride	76902-90-4	Cl salt	Removed Cl and used Pubchem structure
354	Acetic acid, ((3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinyl)oxy)-, compd. with N,N-diethylethanamine (1:1)	57213-69-1	Mixtures so not suitable for QSAR	Removed
356	Acifluorfen, sodium	62476-59-9	Na salt	Keep, but used parent structure
366	Boric acid	10043-35-3	Not suitable for QSAR	Removed
372	Clofencet	82697-71-0	CAS is K salt, use parent (CAS 129025-54-3)	Used parent but kept CAS
375	Copper, bis[1-cyclohexyl-1,2-di(hydroxy-kappa.O)diazoniumato(2-)]-	312600-89-8	Not suitable for QSAR	Removed
376	Cryolite	15096-52-3	Not suitable for QSAR	Removed
387	Didecyldimethylammonium chloride	7173-51-5	Salt. Remove Cl (used parent CAS 20256-56-8)	Keep, but used parent structure
388	Difenzoquat metilsulfate	43222-48-6	Salt	Keep, but used parent structure
393	Diquat dibromide	85-00-7	Salt	Keep, but used parent structure
398	Ethylenebisdithiocarbamate, disodium	142-59-6	Salt	Keep, but used parent structure (CAS 111-54-6)
400	Flucarbazone-sodium	181274-17-9	Salt	Keep, but used parent structure (CAS 145026-88-

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
				6)
406	Formetanate hydrochloride	23422-53-9	Salt – when remove HCl becomes duplicate with A/A 140	Removed but used results from A/A 140
407	Glufosinate-ammonium	77182-82-2	Salt	Keep, but used parent structure (CAS 51276-47-2)
417	Lithium hypochlorite	13840-33-0	Not suitable for QSAR	Removed
418	Mancozeb	8018-01-7	Salt – when remove HCl becomes duplicate with A/A 398	Removed but used results from A/A 398
420	Mecoprop-P	93-65-2	K Salt not suitable for QSAR. If remove salt then is duplicate with AA 419	Removed, but used results from A/A 419
434	Phosphoric acid, bis(2-ethylhexyl) ester, compd. with 2,2'-(coco alkylimino)bis(ethanol)	68649-38-7	Mixture, not suitable in silico	Removed
435	Potassium dimethyldithiocarbamate	128-03-0	Salt	Keep, but used parent structure (CAS 79-45-8)
440	Propoxycarbazone-sodium	181274-15-7	Salt	Keep, but used parent structure (CAS 145026-81-9)
442	Pyriithiobac-sodium	123343-16-8	Salt	Keep, but used parent structure (CAS 123342-93-8)
444	S-Bioallethrin	28434-00-6	2D structure is duplicate of AA 296	Removed but used results from AA 296
448	Tetrakis(hydroxymethyl)phosphonium sulfate	55566-30-8	Salt	Keep, but used parent structure (CAS 24655-84-3 Tetrakis)
454	Tributyltetradecylphosphonium chloride	81741-28-8	Cl salt	Convert to neutral parent

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
455	Trifloxysulfuron-sodium	199119-58-9	Na salt	Convert to neutral parent (CAS 145099-21-4)
463	Aluminium sulphate	20859-73-8	Inorganic so not suitable QSAR	removed
466	Calcium phosphide	1305-99-3	Inorganic so not suitable QSAR	removed
476	Milbemectin	51596-10-2 (milbemycin A3) + 51596-11-3 (milbemycin A4)	Two different compounds, just selected one that comes from name search (CAS 51596-10-2)	Use first structure (CAS 51596-10-2)
480	Sodium 5-nitroguaiacolate	67233-85-6	Na salt not suitable	Used parent (CAS 636-93-1)
481	Sodium hypochlorite	7681-52-9	Inorganic	removed
483	Sodium p-nitrophenolate	824-78-2	Duplicate when remove Na salt with A/A 482	Removed, but use results from A/A 482
486	Zinc phosphide	1314-84-7	Inorganic	removed
493	camphechlor	8001-35-2	Mixture of polychlorinated derivatives, unspecified structure in Chemidplus	Used the example in Pubchem which comes up when search using the CAS

Table A2. Biocides (A/A numbers refer to latest version of Chemical Inventory at the time of writing 5 9 2016)

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
1	Abamectin	71751-41-2	Mixture of 2 compounds, not suitable in silico	Removed
3	alpha - Cypermethrin	67375-30-8	Stereoisomer of A/A 69 so duplicate	Removed
4	Aluminium phosphide	20859-73-8	Metal complex, not suitable in silico	Removed

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
20	Magnesium phosphide	12057-74-8	Not suitable in silico	Removed
23	Spinosad	168316-95-8	Mixture, not suitable	Removed
30	Carbamodithioic acid, cyano-, disodium salt	138-93-2	Na salt	Convert to neutral parent (CAS 108-04-3)
31	Chlorhexidine diacetate	56-95-1	salt	Remove diacetate. Used parent (CAS 55-56-1)
32	Zinc pyrithione	13463-41-7	Zn complex, not suitable QSAR	Removed
34	Polixetonium chloride	31512-74-0	Polymer so not suitable QSAR	Removed

Table A3. NIAS_FCM compounds (A/A numbers refer to latest version of Chemical Inventory at the time of writing 5 9 2016)

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
11	Nonylphenol	25154-52-3	The nonyl group can be attached to the phenol ring at various locations (not specified in ChemIDPlus). Usually at the 4-position, sometimes at 2-position and can be branched or linear. A branched 4-nonylphenol is most produced (Wikipedia) so used Pubchem structure (4-(2,6-dimethylheptyl)phenol)	Used Pubchem structure
24	Dibutyl phthalate	84-74-2	Duplicate of A/A 14	Removed, used results from AA 14
25	Divinylbenzene	1321-74-0	Structure not specified	Removed, see results for 3 possible structural isomers A/A 26, 27 and 28
32	Sodium selenite	10102-18-8	Not suitable in silico	Removed
35	Tricresyl phosphate	1330-78-5	CAS is for mixture of isomers.	Selected one isomer (Me gpds in para position) CAS 78-32-

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
				0
37	Vinyl toluene	25013-15-4	CAS is for mixture of isomers	Selected one isomer (3-vinyl toluene) CAS 100-80-1
39	4,4'-Diamino-2,20-stilbenedisulfonic acid, disodium salt	81-11-8	Na salt	Convert to parent
45	Barium chloride hydrate	10326-27-9	Not suitable in silico	Removed
46	Styrene-acrylonitrile trimer	9003-54-7	Not suitable in silico	Removed
48	3,30-Dimethoxybenzidine ochloride	20325-40-0	Cl salt	Convert to parent (CAS 119-90-4)
52	Sodium dichromate dihydrate (VI)	7789-12-0	Not suitable in silico	Removed
60	Dipropylene glycol	25265-71-8	ChemiPlus structure not correct	Used structure from Pubchem

Table A4. Other compounds (A/A numbers refer to latest version of Chemical Inventory at the time of writing 5 9 2016)

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
1	(2S)-4,4-difluoro-1-{N-[8-(pyrimidin-2-yl)-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]oct-3-yl]glycyl}pyrrolidine-2-carbonitrile	NO CAS_47346	Found by name Chemspider	Downloaded from Chemspider
4	1-[(2Z)-3-(2-chloro-3-methoxybiphenyl-4-yl)prop-2-en-1-yl]azepane hydrochloride (1:1)	NO CAS_47342	Found by NO CAS_47342 Chemspider	Downloaded from Chemspider . Removed HCl
7	2,4-Diaminophenodihydrochloride	137-09-7	HCl salt	Used parent (CAS 95-86-3)
9	3,3'-Dimethylbenzidine dihydrochloride	612-82-8	salt	Used parent (CAS 119-93-7)
11	3-chloro-2-[(3R)-5-chloro-1-(2,4-	NO CAS_47379	Found by NO	Downloaded

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
	dimethoxybenzyl)-3-methyl-2-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-indol-3-yl]-N-ethyl-N-(pyridin-3-ylmethyl)benzamide hydrochloride		CAS_47379 Chemspider	from Chemspider . Removed HCl
14	4,4'-Methylenedianiline dihydrochloride	13552-44-8	HCl salt	Used parent (CAS 101-77-9)
16	5-fluoro-1-(3-fluorobenzyl)-N-(1H-indol-5-yl)-1H-indole-2-carboxamide	NO CAS_47366	Found by name Chemspider	Downloaded from Chemspider
18	6-(5-(((2S)-2-(4-fluorophenyl)-4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl)furan-3-yl)-1,3-benzoxazol-2-ol hydrochloride hydrate	NO CAS_47349	Found by NO CAS ChemSpider	Downloaded from Chemspider . Removed HCl and H2O
19	6-chloro-2-phenyl-8,8a-dihydro-3aH-indeno[1,2-d][1,3]thiazol-3a-ol	NO CAS_47338	Found by NO CAS ChemSpider	Downloaded from Chemspider
20	8-prenylnaringenin (8-PN)	421848 (is 53846-50-7)	No structure available ChemIDPlus	Structure, MW and SMILES codes from Pubchem
28	Ammonium bromide	12124-97-9	Not suitable QSAR	Removed
30	Benzophenone	119-61-9	Duplicate of PPP A/A 363	Used results from PPP A/A 363
34	Boric acid	10043-35-3	Duplicate of PPP A/A 366 Structure not suitable QSAR	Removed
38	C.I. Acid red 114	6459-94-5	Na salt not suitable for QSAR	Used parent (CAS 25317-45- 7)
39	C.I. Direct blue 15	2429-74-5	Na salt not suitable for QSAR	Used parent (Pubchem)
40	C.I. Direct blue 218	28407-37-6	Cu and Na salt not suitable for QSAR	Used parent (Pubchem)
41	Carbamodithioic acid, cyano-, disodium salt	138-93-2	Na salt not suitable for QSAR Duplicate of Biocides AA 30	Removed, used results from Biocide A/A 30
42	Cariporide mesylate (HOE642)	159138-81-5	salt	Used Parent (CAS 159138-80-

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
				4)
43	CD3254	196961-43-0	No structure available ChemIDPlus	Structure, MW and SMILES codes from Pubchem
44	Coumarin	91-64-5	Duplicate of PPP AA 458	Removed, used QSAR results from PPP AA 458
47	Dichromic acid, (H ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇), disodium salt, dihydrate	7789-12-0	Cr salt. Not suitable QSAR	Removed
50	Diphenhydramine hydrochloride	147-24-0	HCl salt	Used parent (CAS 58-73-1)
51	Dipropylene glycol	25265-71-8	Duplicate of NIAS_FCM AA 60	Removed, used QSAR results from NIAS_FCM AA 60
56	ethyl (2R,3S)-3-amino-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1-benzofuran-2-carboxylate	NOCAS_47362	Found chemspider	Used Chemspider structure
59	fadrozole	102676-31-3	This CAS is for HCl salt	Used parent (CAS 102676-47-1)
62	Formamide	75-12-7	Duplicate of PPP AA 405	Removed, used QSAR results from PPP AA 405
65	Gallium arsenide	1303-00-0	Inorganic not suitable QSAR	Removed
68	Heparan sulfate	57459-72-0	Structure not specified ChemIDPlus, use Pubchem	Used PubChem structure
69	Heparin	9005-49-6	Corrected CAS in database	Chemidplus structure
75	Indium phosphide	22398-80-7	Inorganic not suitable QSAR	Removed
80	Malachite green	569-64-2	Cl salt not suitable QSAR	Used parent structure (cation, CAS 10309-95-2)

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
84	Methyleugenol	93-15-2	Duplicate of PPP AA 423	Removed, used QSAR results from PPP AA 423
85	methylmercury chloride		Not suitable QSAR	Removed
90	N-[(S)-(3S)-1-azabicyclo[2.2.2]oct-3-yl(phenyl)methyl]-2,6-dichloro-3-(trifluoromethyl)benzamide hydrochloride (1:1)	NOCAS_47364	Found by NO CAS_47364 Chemspider	Downloaded from Chemspider . Removed HCl
92	Nickel (II) oxide		Inorganic not suitable QSAR	Removed
93	Nickel sulfate hexahydrate		Inorganic not suitable QSAR	Removed
96	Pfizer_Pharma_CP-395919	NOCAS_Pfizer7	Can't find in any of databases	Removed
97	Pfizer_Pharma_CP-449122	NOCAS_Pfizer18	Can't find in any of databases	Removed
98	Pfizer_Pharma_CP-601927	NOCAS_Pfizer19	Can't find in any of databases	Removed
99	Polihexanide	32289-58-0	Polymeric so not suitable QSAR	Removed
100	Polysorbate 80	9005-65-6	Chemidplus structure problem	Structure from Chemspider
103	Quinine hydrochloride	7549-43-1	HCl salt so not suitable QSAR	Used parent structure (CAS 130-95-0)
104	Raloxifene hydrochloride	82640-04-8	HCl salt so not suitable QSAR	Used parent structure (CAS 84449-90-1)
105	SnCl ₂	7772-99-8	Inorganic not suitable QSAR	Removed
106	Sodium azide	26628-22-8	Inorganic not suitable QSAR	Removed
107	sodium salicylate (SAL)	54-21-7	Na salt not suitable QSAR	Use parent (CAS 69-72-7)
112	Trientine hydrochloride	38260-01-4	HCl salt so not suitable QSAR	Used parent (CAS 112-24-3)
117	Vanadium oxide	1314-62-1	Inorganic not suitable	Removed

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
			QSAR	
119	Volinanserin desmethyl metabolite	139290-65-6_metabolite	Structure of metabolite not known	Removed
124	Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride	93107-08-5	HCl salt	Used parent (CAS 85721-33-1)
126	Enalapril maleate	76095-16-4	salt	Used parent (CAS 75847-73-3)
127	Ranitidine hydrochloride	66357-59-3	HCl salt	Use parent (CAS 66357-35-5)
132	Labetalol hydrochloride	32780-64-6	HCl salt	Use parent (CAS 36894-69-6)
136	Diclofenac sodium	15307-79-6	Na salt	Use parent (CAS 15307-86-5)
137	Perhexiline maleate	6724-53-4	salt	Used parent (CAS 6621-47-2)
142	Tacrine hydrochloride	1684-40-8	HCl salt	Used parent (CAS 321-64-2)
143	Gentamicin sulfate	1405-41-0	salt	Used parent (CAS 1403-66-3)
144	Vancomycin hydrochloride	1404-93-9	HCl salt	Use parent (CAS 1404-90-6)
146	Sodium valproate	1069-66-5	Na salt	If use parent becomes duplicate so removed
147	Moxisylyte hydrochloride	964-52-3	HCl salt	Used parent (CAS 54-32-0)
151	Oxydemeton-methyl	301-12-2	Duplicate of PPP AA 421	Removed, used results from PPP AA 421
152	Fluphenazine hydrochloride	146-56-5	HCl salt	Used parent (CAS 69-23-8)
154	Thioridazine hydrochloride	130-61-0	HCl salt	Used parent (CAS 50-52-2)
161	Cephalothin sodium	58-71-9	Na salt	Use parent (CAS 153-61-7)

A/A	Compound name	CAS	Comments	Outcome
172	(2-methyl-4-oxo-3-penta-2,4-dienylcyclopent-2-en-1-yl) 3-(3-methoxy-2-methyl-3-oxoprop-1-enyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylate		Pyrethrin II? When search on name in Chemspider is the same structure	Used pyrethrin 11 (CAS 121-29-9)
180	4,4'-hexane-1,5-diylidiphenol	1941-86-2	CAS incorrect in July inventory (should be 5776-72-7?). Is duplicate of AA 74	Wasn't included in QSAR analysis by mistake – run later
184	2-[2-(4-Nonylphenoxy)ethoxy]ethanol	68412-54-4	Structure not specified in Chemidplus	Downloaded from Pubchem
205	3-hydroxy-2-methoxybenzaldehyde	66495-88-3	Structure not specified in Chemidplus	Downloaded from Pubchem
218	T0901317	293754-55-9	Not available Chemidplus	Downloaded from Pubchem
219	SR9238	1416153-62-2	Not available Chemidplus / Pubchem	Downloaded from Chemspider
220	Chromium (VI)	18540-29-9	Inorganic	Removed
221	Di-n-hexyl phthalate (DnHP)	84-75-3	Duplicate of NIAS_FCM AA 56	Removed, used results from NIAS_FCM AA 56

Nb. All Mycotoxin, Alkaloid and Environmental Pollutant structures were suitable for QSAR and no changes to the chemical structures were made.

Annex 2. Model details of C4.5 CDK Decision tree model for hepatotoxicity developed at Fera

C4.5 CDK Decision tree model for hepatotoxicity.

Training set: Pizzo dataset.(Pizzo et al 2015)

Test set:randomly selected 30% of the Pizzo dataset

Calculation of CDK descriptors:CDK Descriptor GUI
(<http://www.rguha.net/code/java/cdkdesc.html>)

Chemical Development Kit (CDK):<https://sourceforge.net/projects/cdk/>

Model development: TANAGRA (<http://eric.univ-lyon2.fr/~ricco/tanagra/>)

Model outline:

Model detail:

1. Dataset: Pizzo dataset (see above), with all CDK descriptors
2. Define status: All CDK descriptors as input; hepatotoxicity status (positive or negative) as target.
3. Runs filtering: selection of best input variables, using a supervised cutting rule algorithm.
4. The c4.5 Decision tree. (C4.5: Programs for Machine Learning by J. Ross Quinlan, Machine Learning, September 1994, Volume 16, Issue 3, pp 235–240)
5. Train Test. Repeat of the model using 70% of the dataset to train and 30% to test.

Model Results

1 Variable selection

INPUT selection	
Before filtering	269
After filtering	5

Keeped into INPUT selection

Attributes	
1	ALogP
2	ALogp2
3	AMR
4	BCUTw-1l
5	BCUTw-1h

2. C4.5 Model Performance with full training set.

Classifier performances

Error rate			0.2392			
Values prediction			Confusion matrix			
Value	Recall	1-Precision		hepatotoxic	non-hepatotoxic	Sum
hepatotoxic	0.8966	0.2676	hepatotoxic	104	12	116
non-hepatotoxic	0.5914	0.1791	non-hepatotoxic	38	55	93
			Sum	142	67	209

Classifier characteristics

Data description

Target attribute	Measured (2 values)
# descriptors	5

Tree description

Number of nodes	31
Number of leaves	16

Decision tree

- BCUTw-1h < 34.9719
 - ALogP < 1.2273
 - ALogP < -2.8415 then Measured = hepatotoxic (100.00 % of 6 examples)
 - ALogP >= -2.8415
 - AMR < 17.2669 then Measured = hepatotoxic (100.00 % of 5 examples)
 - AMR >= 17.2669
 - BCUTw-1l < 11.9265 then Measured = hepatotoxic (55.00 % of 40 examples)
 - BCUTw-1l >= 11.9265
 - BCUTw-1h < 15.9979 then Measured = hepatotoxic (100.00 % of 13 examples)
 - BCUTw-1h >= 15.9979
 - BCUTw-1l < 11.9887 then Measured = hepatotoxic (100.00 % of 5 examples)
 - BCUTw-1l >= 11.9887
 - BCUTw-1h < 31.4733
 - BCUTw-1l < 11.9962 then Measured = non-hepatotoxic (85.71 % of 7 examples)
 - BCUTw-1l >= 11.9962
 - ALogp2 < 0.8412 then Measured = hepatotoxic (75.00 % of 20 examples)
 - ALogp2 >= 0.8412 then Measured = non-hepatotoxic (70.00 % of 10 examples)
 - BCUTw-1h >= 31.4733 then Measured = hepatotoxic (73.33 % of 15 examples)
 - ALogP >= 1.2273
 - ALogP < 1.3665 then Measured = non-hepatotoxic (100.00 % of 5 examples)
 - ALogP >= 1.3665
 - AMR < 51.1564 then Measured = hepatotoxic (72.73 % of 22 examples)
 - AMR >= 51.1564
 - BCUTw-1h < 14.0072 then Measured = hepatotoxic (75.00 % of 8 examples)
 - BCUTw-1h >= 14.0072
 - BCUTw-1h < 23.9876 then Measured = non-hepatotoxic (86.96 % of 23 examples)
 - BCUTw-1h >= 23.9876
 - AMR < 85.4492 then Measured = hepatotoxic (62.50 % of 8 examples)
 - AMR >= 85.4492 then Measured = non-hepatotoxic (80.00 % of 5 examples)
- BCUTw-1h >= 34.9719 then Measured = non-hepatotoxic (76.47 % of 17 examples)

3. Model validation:

| Train-test parameters | |
|-----------------------|------|
| Train proportion | 0.70 |
| Trials | 1 |

Results

Dataset size : 209

Tests error rate

| Trial | Train size | Test size | Error rate |
|-------|------------|-----------|------------|
| 1 | 146 | 63 | 0.3175 |

Overall test error rate

| Error rate | | | 0.3175 | | | |
|-------------------|--------|-------------|------------------|-------------|-----------------|-----|
| Values prediction | | | Confusion matrix | | | |
| Value | Recall | 1-Precision | | hepatotoxic | non-hepatotoxic | Sum |
| hepatotoxic | 0.8095 | 0.2609 | hepatotoxic | 34 | 8 | 42 |
| non-hepatotoxic | 0.4286 | 0.4706 | non-hepatotoxic | 12 | 9 | 21 |
| | | | Sum | 46 | 17 | 63 |

The model has good overall predictability, though it errs on the side of false positives. It performs as well as other published models.

Annex 3. Model details of C4.5 CDK Decision tree model for Estrogen Receptor binding developed at Fera

The training set used was the training set for the Relative Binding Affinity model used in VEGA, (www.vega-qsar.eu)

Descriptors used were those from the RDKit, (<http://www.rdkit.org/>)

The construction of the model was similar to that described for the hepatotoxicity model above.

Results:

1. Variable selection: Variable selection used a stepwise discriminant analysis function, and repeated runs showed that the optimum results were obtained with 6 variables as shown below.

| Parameters | |
|-----------------------------|--------|
| Stopping rule | 2 |
| F to enter/remove | 3.8400 |
| Sig. level | 0.0500 |
| Subset size | 6 |
| Search algorithm | |
| Backward (0) or Forward (1) | 1 |
| Report | |
| Show selected subset | 1 |
| Show detailed results | 1 |
| # columns for details | 5 |

Selection results

[6] selected attributes on [117]

Selected attributes' subset

| N° | Selected atts |
|----|---------------|
| 1 | slogp_VSA11 |
| 2 | slogp_VSA1 |
| 3 | MQN30 |
| 4 | MQN6 |
| 5 | peoe_VSA14 |
| 6 | peoe_VSA2 |

2. Model Performance:

| Decision tree (C4.5) parameters | |
|----------------------------------|------|
| Min size of leaves | 5 |
| Confidence-level for pessimistic | 0.25 |

Classifier performances

| Error rate | | | 0.1638 | | | |
|-------------------|--------|-------------|------------------|----------|--------|-----|
| Values prediction | | | Confusion matrix | | | |
| Value | Recall | 1-Precision | | Inactive | Active | Sum |
| Inactive | 0.9151 | 0.1566 | Inactive | 474 | 44 | 518 |
| Active | 0.6944 | 0.1803 | Active | 88 | 200 | 288 |
| | | | Sum | 562 | 244 | 806 |

Classifier characteristics

Data description

| | |
|------------------|-------------------------------|
| Target attribute | Experimental value (2 values) |
| # descriptors | 6 |

Tree description

| | |
|------------------|----|
| Number of nodes | 61 |
| Number of leaves | 31 |

Decision tree

3. Model validation:

Train-test parameters

| | |
|------------------|------|
| Train proportion | 0.70 |
| Trials | 1 |

Dataset size : 806

Tests error rate

| Trial | Train size | Test size | Error rate |
|-------|------------|-----------|------------|
| 1 | 564 | 242 | 0.2149 |

Overall test error rate

| Error rate | | | 0.2149 | | | |
|-------------------|--------|-------------|------------------|----------|--------|-----|
| Values prediction | | | Confusion matrix | | | |
| Value | Recall | 1-Precision | | Inactive | Active | Sum |
| Inactive | 0.8364 | 0.1534 | Inactive | 138 | 27 | 165 |
| Active | 0.6753 | 0.3418 | Active | 25 | 52 | 77 |
| | | | Sum | 163 | 79 | 242 |

The model has good predictivity for both binding (active) and non-binding (inactive) compounds.

Annex 4. Details of Derek Nexus Alerts that mention Steatosis in the Alert description

| Alert # | Class | Alert description |
|---------|--------------------------|--|
| 081 | Aliphatic nitro compound | <p>This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of aliphatic nitro compounds.</p> <p>Aliphatic nitro compounds (or nitroalkanes) are used as solvents in industry. Human fatalities after occupational exposure to nitropropane by inhalation in enclosed environments have been reported [Hine et al, Zimmerman]. In all cases the post-mortem revealed extensive necrosis of hepatocytes, typically centrilobular, and in some cases the fatty degeneration of lobule was observed.</p> <p>Nitromethane, nitroethane and 1-nitropropane have been reported to cause steatosis and necrosis in animals [Zimmerman]. Early studies with nitroalkanes were found to cause liver damage in cat, guinea pig, rabbit and rat by inhalation and intraperitoneal (i.p.) routes [Hine et al]. A single i.p. administration of 2-nitropropane in mice caused significant elevation of hepatic enzymes: sorbitol dehydrogenase, alanine aminotransferase, and aspartic aminotransferase, at doses of 9 mmol/kg. The effects were apparent 48 hours after administration and liver damage was observed in female mice at lower doses. Histopathological examination of the most severely damaged livers showed extensive necrosis with apoptosis and disruption of normal parenchyma [Dayal et al]. The same paper reported that at similar doses nitromethane and nitroethane were much less hepatotoxic.</p> <p>The hepatotoxicity of nitroparaffins may be related to chain length and position of the nitro group [Zimmerman]. Work in guinea pigs and rabbits has shown increasing toxicity and fatty infiltration in the liver with increasing molecular weight [Hine et al]. Secondary nitroalkanes are more reactive and hepatotoxic than primary compounds [Fiala et al, Cunningham and Matthews, Dayal et al, Conaway et al]. The mechanism of hepatotoxicity for this class is not clear, but at physiological pH, nitroalkanes exist in equilibrium with their nitronate anions, which may be the active species. In mutagenicity studies the nitronate forms have been shown to be more reactive [Dayal et al, Conaway et al, Fiala et al].</p> |
| 538 | Tetracycline | <p>"This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of tetracycline compounds. Their main effect is the production of severe microvesicular steatosis.</p> <p>Tetracyclines constitute a group of antibiotics that exhibit activity against a wide range of microorganisms including gram-positive, gram-negative and atypical organisms. These agents interact primarily with the ribosomal complex, inhibiting bacterial protein synthesis [Suarez and Nathans]. Liver injury in humans in the form of microvesicular steatosis has been associated with these drugs [Lepper et al, Peters et al] and this steatogenic effect has also been reported in rats, mice [Zimmerman, Fromenty and Pessayre, Einheber et al, Seto and Lepper, Gotz et al, Steiner et al] and in in vitro studies using canine hepatocytes [Amacher and Martin].</p> <p>The severity of tetracycline-induced steatosis depends on the dose and route of administration. Severe cases have been reported after high intravenous doses (> 1.5 g/day) mainly to pregnant women [Zimmerman, Whalley et al] and men with abnormal renal function [Zimmerman, Robinson and Rywlin]. Experimental studies have, however, failed to clarify the role of pregnancy or gonadal status in susceptibility to the hepatic injury [Breen et al].</p> <p>Doxycycline and minocycline have led to instances of hepatic injury that are strikingly different: doxycycline has led to an instance of cholestatic injury [Zimmerman] and minocycline to at least 20 cases of acute hepatocellular injury and to a number of cases of chronic hepatitis resembling autoimmune hepatitis and macrovesicular steatosis [Burette et</p> |

| | | |
|-----|------------------------|---|
| | | <p>al, Goldstein et al].</p> <p>The structural features that confer antibacterial activity to the tetracyclines are now well established [Chopra and Roberts, Brodersen et al] and are thought to be the same for hepatotoxicity [Zimmerman]. The simplest tetracycline to display detectable antibacterial activity is 6-deoxy-6-demethyltetracycline; its structure has thus been regarded as the minimum pharmacophore [Chopra and Roberts]. Tetracyclines are known to be strong chelating agents: both their antimicrobial and pharmacokinetic properties are influenced by chelation of metal ions. It is probable that the active species is a magnesium-tetracycline complex. Consistent with these aspects, important features can be summarised as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -maintenance of the linear fused tetracyclic nucleus (rings designated as A, B, C and D), -maintenance of the ""alpha"" configurations at position 4, 4a and 12a (A-B ring junction), -conservation of the keto-enol system and the carboxamide known to be involved in the chelation of divalent ions and the hydrogen bonding interactions with the RNA components, -substitutions at different positions on the B, C and D rings are tolerated. <p>In terms of mechanism of toxicity, the microvesicular steatosis induced by tetracyclines may be a consequence of a dual effect: decreased egress of triglycerides from the liver and inhibition of mitochondrial beta-oxidation [Fromenty and Pessayre, Labbe et al, Freneaux et al]. In addition, several studies have shown that tetracyclines were able to impair the mitochondrial respiratory chain and oxidative phosphorylation in rat and mouse mitochondria [Fromenty and Pessayre]."</p> |
| 546 | Short chain fatty acid | <p>"This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of short chain fatty acids. These compounds, as exemplified by valproic acid (VPA), have been associated with a steatogenic effect on the liver [Nelson].</p> <p>Valproic acid is a small branched chain fatty acid used in several forms of seizure disorders. An asymptomatic increase in serum aminotransferase activity that normalizes with either dose reduction or drug discontinuation has been noted in up to 44% of recipients [Zimmerman and Ishak, Fromenty and Pessayre 1995]. A much less frequent effect is a Reye-like syndrome which has been noted mainly, but not exclusively, in children [Konig et al, Scheffner et al]. This severe and usually fatal form of hepatotoxicity is not clearly dose-dependent [Scheffner et al, Zimmerman and Ishak, Dreifuss et al]. It has been associated with microvesicular steatosis accompanied by centrilobular necrosis, inflammatory infiltrates and cirrhosis [Zimmerman and Ishak]. Intrahepatic cholestasis and ductular proliferation have also been reported [Zimmerman and Ishak]. Polytherapy with other antiepileptic drugs, pre-existing liver conditions and metabolic disturbances may increase susceptibility [Fromenty and Pessayre 1995] or play a role in the noted necrotic effects [Zimmerman]. Hypoglycin, a methylenecyclopropylpropionic acid derivative has also been incriminated in cases of Jamaican vomiting sickness, a condition that shares similarities with the classical Reye's syndrome [Zimmerman]. Amineptine and tianeptine are two antidepressants bearing an identical heptanoic side chain. Cases of microvesicular steatosis have been reported with amineptine and to a lesser extend with tianeptine usually administered at lower doses [Fromenty and Pessayre 1995].</p> <p>Microvesicular steatosis has been reproduced in rats and mice with valproic acid only following pre-treatment with enzymes inducers [Kesterson et al, Lewis et al]. Similar effects have been observed with some unsaturated metabolites of VPA, cyclopropane carboxylic acid, amineptine and tianeptine [Kesterson et al, Lewis et al, Glasgow and Chase, Fromenty et al, Jolly et al, Le Dinh et al, Letteron et al].</p> <p>Mitochondrial toxicity is thought to be a possible mechanism for the observed effect [Jolly et al, Fromenty and Pessayre 1995, Kesterson et al]. Like natural fatty acids, those compounds and/or related metabolites may undergo mitochondrial beta-oxidation. This can lead to a depletion of the intracellular pool of CoA and carnitine, thus impairing the beta-oxidation of natural fatty acids. Another potential mechanism is thought to involve the irreversible</p> |

| | | |
|-----|----------------------------|--|
| | | <p>deactivation of mitochondrial enzymes by reactive diene and enone intermediates formed from the omega-oxidation pathway [Fromenty and Pessayre 1995, Fromenty and Pessayre 1997, Nelson].</p> <p>The alert patterns have been defined for carboxylic acid compounds bearing a 5 to 7 carbon chain. Essential features include i) the 2, 4-dienic bond and alkyl branches (Me, Et and Pr) for the pentanoic acid skeleton and ii) any omega-pathway metabolites. The cyclopropane carboxylic acid structure is included. Butyric acid is omitted on the basis that it has not induced steatosis in rats [Jolly et al]."</p> |
| 551 | Salicylic acid or analogue | <p>"This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of salicylic acid and its analogues. In humans salicylates cause liver injury such as cholestatic hepatitis, steatosis and necrosis [Deltenre et al, Hamdan et al, Seaman et al, Sochocky]. In animals the effect of salicylates on the liver is varied, the elevation of liver enzymes was not always accompanied by histopathological results [Webb and Hansen, Tomoda et al, Mehrotra and Sarna]. The mechanism of toxicity of salicylates is not clear, some compounds have shown idiosyncratic effects, while aspirin toxicity is thought to have an intrinsic character.</p> <p>Salicylates possess anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic properties and they are mainly used for treatment of rheumatism, rheumatic fever, juvenile rheumatoid arthritis and systemic lupus erythematosus [Seaman et al]. The most frequently used salicylate is the acetylsalicylic acid, commonly known as aspirin [Zimmerman].</p> <p>The hepatotoxicity of salicylates appears to have a (reversible) dose-dependent pattern [Zimmerman, Hamdan et al, Tolman], i.e. on cessation of the medication the hepatic effects are dramatically reduced. Increased alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) levels are commonly seen accompanying the toxic response [Bernstein et al, Cook et al, Deltenre et al, Hamdan et al, Seaman et al]. Case reports about aspirin-induced liver damage in patients with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (daily dose over 74 mg/kg) and lupus erythematosus (2-3.6 g/day) have been reported in the literature [Seaman et al, Bernstein et al]. The implication of aspirin in Reye's syndrome, a fatal illness associated with the accumulation of fat in the liver (steatosis), is well documented [Zimmerman]. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) requires a labelling warning about Reye's syndrome on drugs containing aspirin and non-aspirin salicylates [FDA]. Other salicylate derivatives like 5-aminosalicylic acid, also known as mesalazine [Deltenre et al], and diflunisal [Cook et al] have been reported to cause chronic hepatitis and significant increase in AST and ALT at daily doses of 300 mg and 1000 mg respectively. Results of in vitro cytotoxicity studies with diflunisal using rat hepatocytes correlate with the toxic response reported in humans [Masubuchi et al]. Cases of massive liver necrosis were reported in patients treated with 4-aminosalicylic acid (daily dose of 12 g) and isoniazid for pulmonary tuberculosis [Sochocky]. Two out of three cases of liver necrosis were attributed to 4-aminosalicylic acid [Sochocky].</p> <p>Liver changes were observed in rats fed (ad libitum) with 4-aminosalicylic acid for 10 weeks. Morphological changes included swollen cells with intensive vacuolation containing macronuclei or 2-3 nucleoli [Mehrotra and Sarna]. An administration of aspirin or sodium salicylate to rabbits caused an increase in plasma levels of enzymes, however liver damage was noticed histopathologically only in some animals [Janota et al]. Moderate microvesicular steatosis due to methylsalicylate was reported to occur in dogs, but not in rats or rabbits [Webb and Hansen]. Effects on mitochondrial function without histopathological changes were observed in rats treated with 50-150 mg/kg of acetylsalicylate [Tomoda et al]. Results of in vitro cytotoxic studies with diflunisal using rat hepatocytes correlate with the toxic response reported in humans [Masubuchi et al].</p> <p>The mechanism of toxicity of this class is not fully understood but a number of mechanisms have been proposed. Aspirin is reported to have intrinsic toxicity with a recommended maximum safe dose for adults of less than 300 mg daily [O'Connor et al]. Aspirin was also shown to uncouple oxidative phosphorylation in isolated hepatocytes [Trost and Lemasters,</p> |

| | | |
|-----|----------------------|---|
| | | <p>Petrescu and Tarba]. Inhibition of succinate dehydrogenase and alpha-ketoglutarate dehydrogenase in the Krebs cycle by salicylates has also been suggested to be involved in the mechanism of hepatotoxicity [Mogilevskaya et al]. For diflunisal and 4-aminosalicylic acid a hypersensitivity reaction was proposed to be the causative reason for hepatotoxicity [Cook et al, Sochocky].</p> <p>The scope of the alert is based on the chemical features shared by the compounds discussed."</p> |
| 553 | Formamide derivative | <p>This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of formamide derivatives.</p> <p>Formamide derivatives are known occupational toxicants that have been reported with a dose-dependent hepatocellular injury in the form of necrosis and/or microvesicular steatosis. Typical examples include dimethylformamide (DMF) and N-methylformamide (NMF) which are mainly used as solvents and synthons in chemical syntheses [Zimmerman, Redlich et al].</p> <p>The toxic effect has been reproduced with NMF in mice and rats [Lundberg et al, Whitby et al] and with DMF in several species including mice which have given a positive response only after large doses or repeated exposure to the chemical [Zimmerman, Craig et al, Kestell et al, van den Bulcke]. Additionally, histological evidence for hepatic necrosis accompanied by increased sorbitol dehydrogenase activity has been observed with DMF regardless of the route of administration [Zimmerman, Kennedy and Sherman]. N-Ethylformamide and N-hydroxymethyl-N-methylformamide are other related compounds that have also been associated with liver toxicity in mice and rats respectively [Kestell et al, van den Bulcke et al].</p> <p>It is thought that N-alkylcarbamic acid thioester conjugates, which are formed during the metabolism of N-alkylformamides in mammalian systems, may act as important mediators of the hepatotoxicity of the parent formamides, possibly through their ability to liberate the highly reactive methyl isocyanate at cell membranes [Kalgutkar et al].</p> <p>The present alert includes any formamide derivatives which can be metabolised to a reactive isocyanate intermediate. Tertiary formamides where R1= Me are included as the N-demethylation pathway can easily lead to the active demethylated derivative, as is thought to be the case with DMF [Kalgutkar et al]. The scope of the alert also covers complex structures like N-formylamphetamine and N-(1-Methyl-3,3-diphenylpropyl)formamide, which have been reported to cause liver toxicity and to form sulphhydryl conjugates in rats [Kalgutkar et al, Borel and Abbott]. Formamide itself is excluded as no effects have been observed in mice and rats [Kestell et al, Lundberg et al].</p> |
| 554 | Retinoid or analogue | <p>"This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of retinoids and their analogues. Typical examples include vitamin A, also known as retinol, isotretinoin and etretinate which have been reported with distinct patterns of liver injury [Fallon and Boyer].</p> <p>Hypervitaminosis A has been associated with liver toxicity following food or medical intoxication. Many cases have involved individuals who had been ingesting vitamin A as therapy for skin diseases or as a form of faddism [Zimmerman, Fallon and Boyer]. The toxic response has been reported to be dose- and duration-dependent and to resolve upon cessation of the drug [Nolleaux et al, Fallon and Boyer]. Although doses as low as 15000 IU/d have been incriminated in many cases, chronic intoxication has mainly been noted with doses exceeding 40000 IU/d [Zimmerman]. Elevations in aspartate aminotransferase (AST) in up to 70% of recipients, jaundice, hepatomegaly, steatosis, fibrosis, cirrhosis with or without portal hypertension and peliosis-like changes are clinical findings that have been documented [Fallon and Boyer, Nolleaux et al, Zimmerman]. Isotretinoin has only caused mild increases in aminotransferases in 5-35% of patients receiving 0.5-3 mg/kg of the drug for up to 6 months [Fallon and Boyer]. Similar results have been demonstrated in children with high-risk solid tumours and treated with 1050-3300 mg/m² of fenretinide which is a synthetic retinamide [Villablanca et al]. Etretinate is another retinoid compound which has been associated with chronic hepatitis sometimes accompanied by bile duct injury and cirrhosis [Fallon and Boyer].</p> |

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| | | <p>The toxic response in the form of necrosis, fibrosis, steatosis, inflammatory changes and cellular degeneration has been reproduced in rats or mice given retinyl acetate (250mg for 120 and 180 days), etretinate (0.5 and 6 mg/kg/d for 12 weeks) or synthetic retinamides (LD50 doses for 21 days) [McCormick et al, Amo Bernal et al, Sani and Meeks]. However, studies with fenretinide have led to mixed results [Moon et al, Sani and Meeks].</p> <p>Vitamin A-induced hepatotoxicity is thought to result from the action of the parent compound or a metabolite on hepatic stellate cells (HSCs) where retinoids are primarily stored as esters [Senoo, Moon et al]. It has been shown that hypervitaminosis A can trigger HSC hyperplasia and transdifferentiation which is known to be a key event in the pathobiology of fibrogenesis [Nolleaux et al, Gressner and Weiskirchen]. The mechanism by which isotretinoin, fenretinide and etretinate cause hepatic abnormalities is not clear but it is likely that free acidic retinoids, like isotretinoin, alter glycoprotein synthesis or genomic expression and induce non specific damage to cellular membranes [Fallon and Boyer].</p> <p>The scope of the alert is based on the chemical features shared by the compound discussed and is primarily limited to geometric isomers (cis and trans) and precursors of vitamin A and etretinate. Beta-carotene derivatives are excluded as no effects have been observed following excess ingestion [Fallon and Boyer]."</p> |
| 611 | Phenothiazine or thioxanthene derivative | <p>"This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of phenothiazine and thioxanthene derivatives.</p> <p>These compounds are used as antipsychotic agents and have been reported to cause cholestatic jaundice in up to 1% of recipients [Zimmerman]. No dose-response relationships have been clearly established [Reinhart et al]. The hepatic injury observed with chlorpromazine (CPZ), the most studied compound, has been of a hepatocanalicular type [Zelman]. CPZ-induced jaundice has been mainly reflected by elevations in alkaline phosphatase (ALP), bilirubin and aminotransferase level [Hollister, Dickes et al, Moradpur et al]. Clinical signs of hypersensitivity including eosinophilia, secretory antibodies, positive rechallenge with the drug and cross-reactivity between some agents have been noted [Hollister, Quismorio et al, Reinhart et al]. Occasionally, necrosis, fibrosis and a syndrome resembling primary biliary cirrhosis have also been described [Zelman, Moradpur et al]. Like thioridazine and compazine [Barancik et al, McFarland], thioxanthenes including chlorprothixene, thiothixene and flupenthixol appear to produce the icterogenic effect less frequently [Zimmerman]. This suggests that intrinsic toxicity coupled with systemic hypersensitivity may lead to the hepatic disease.</p> <p>Following CPZ administration, adverse reactions including injury to the hepatic cells, steatosis and/or interference with bile secretion have been observed in dogs, rabbits, primates and to a lesser extent in rats [Sharma and Prasad, Knodell, Ros et al, Zimmerman]. Mullock et al have also detected an immune response associated with the release of antibodies to CPZ in rats. Additionally, in vitro studies using isolated rat hepatocytes, rabbit liver slices or Chang liver cells have demonstrated the cytotoxicity and/or the cholestatic effect of CPZ and related compounds [Zimmerman and Kendler, Abernathy and Zimmerman, Munyon et al].</p> <p>The scope of the alert is based on the common structural features shared by these antipsychotic agents. The variations associated with R1 and R2 are defined accordingly to in vitro data providing evidence for a relationship between the potential of these agents for cytotoxicity and various substituents at positions 2 and 10 [Zimmerman and Kendler]."</p> |
| 613 | Arylsulphonylurea or analogue | <p>This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of arylsulphonylureas and their analogues. These compounds have been reported with hepatocellular and/or cholestatic injuries in humans [Zimmerman].</p> <p>Arylsulphonylureas and their analogues are used for the treatment of diabetes mellitus type 2. They act by increasing insulin release from functioning pancreatic beta-cells [Koski].</p> <p>Although diabetes mellitus may be associated with hepatic abnormalities, these drugs cause</p> |

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| | | <p>different forms of liver damage. The clinical signs of hepatic disease observed with diabetes mellitus are steatosis and nonalcoholic steatohepatitis [Zimmerman]. Arylsulphonylureas have been reported with cases of hepatocellular and/or cholestatic injuries combined with jaundice and generalized hypersensitivity [Schneider et al, Zimmerman]. Mild to significant increases in hepatic enzymes accompanied by histological marks of necrosis, granulomatous, bile stasis and portal inflammation have been noted [Bloodworth, Mach et al, Nakao et al, Saw et al, Schneider et al, Zimmerman]. A dose-response relationship has been established with chlorpropamide and metahexamide [Schneider et al, Zimmerman]. Other typical examples include glyburide and tolazamide which has also induced a syndrome resembling primary biliary cirrhosis [Saw et al, Nakao et al]. Due to fatal effects, metahexamide, carbutamide and glythiazol, another structurally related compound, have been removed from clinical use [Mach et al, Zimmerman].</p> <p>Hepatic reactions in the form of hepatomegaly and disturbance of the clotting mechanism have been reproduced in diabetic dogs following prolonged administration of carbutamide [Sirek et al].</p> <p>The mechanism of sulphonylurea-induced hepatotoxicity has not been clearly defined [Nakao et al, Zimmerman]. Hypersensitivity and/or intrinsic toxicity have been thought to play a role in the pathogenesis [Zimmerman]. When comparing compounds, a greater effect has been noted with compounds bearing an amino or a chlorine group [Nakao et al, Zimmerman]. However, hepatic dysfunctions have been reported with glymidine, a non-substituted derivative and other agents which are para-substituted with an alkyl moiety [Zimmerman].</p> <p>The scope of the alerts is based on the shared chemical features of the compounds discussed, some consideration of potential precursors of the amino function (nitroreduction, hydrolysis of N-acetyl groups or oxidative N-dealkylation) and on the structural specificity of glybuthiazol and glymidine.</p> |
| 615 | Hydrazine | <p>This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of hydrazine derivatives. These compounds are known to cause a hepatocellular type injury both in experimental animals (necrosis and/or steatosis) and in humans (necrosis).</p> <p>Hydrazine derivatives are used as synthetic intermediates in the chemical industry, and as therapeutic agents for the treatment of tuberculosis, depression and cancer [Zimmerman, Hussain and Frazier].</p> <p>Typical hepatotoxins include hydrazine itself, isoniazid (INH), iproniazid and hydralazine. The injury has been reflected by significant elevations in aminotransferase levels and/or necrosis [Zimmerman, Black and Hussain]. Hepatic steatosis subsequent to occupational exposure to hydrazines has also been described [Zimmerman]. Age and the use of P450 inducers such as alcohol are thought to enhance susceptibility whereas the role of genetic polymorphism remains controversial [Zimmerman]. In general, no dose-response relationship has been established. Iproniazid has been withdrawn from use because of a high incidence of case reports [Zimmerman, Kahn and Perez]. INH has been associated with biochemical evidence of hepatic injury and overt hepatitis in up to 20% and 2% of recipients respectively [Anonymous, Zimmerman, Black et al]. Hydralazine has caused additional hepatic dysfunctions in the form of granulomas, cholangitis and cholestasis [Zimmerman, Myers and Augur]. Clinical signs of hypersensitivity (fever, rash, eosinophilia, positive rechallenge with the offending drug and detection of antibodies) have also been observed with hydralazine [Zimmerman].</p> <p>Steatosis and/or necrosis have been reproduced in several species with hydrazine [Patrick and Back, Swiecicki et al, Richards et al, Yard and Mckennis], in rats with iproniazid [Nelson et al] and mainly in rabbits with related compounds [Patrick and Back, Nelson et al, Yard and Mckennis]. Additionally, some derivatives have been associated with apparent hepatocarcinogenicity [Zimmerman].</p> |

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| | | <p>Hydrazine-induced hepatotoxicity has been proven to require metabolic activation by the cytochrome P450 system [Timbrell, Kalgutkar et al]. The proposed mechanism involves the monosubstituted hydrazine moiety borne by or derived from the parent compound. Following N-hydroxylation and spontaneous hydrolysis, a diazine intermediate is generated. The latter may undergo homolytic cleavage or an oxidation process leading to free radicals or electrophilic entities (carbonium ions, acylating and diazonium species) [Timbrell, Kalgutkar et al]. Alternatively, a mechanism that could be mediated by the release of reactive oxygen species and subsequent oxidative stress has been suggested [Hussain and Frazier].</p> <p>The scope of the alert is based on i) the chemical features shared by the compounds discussed, ii) some consideration of potential precursors (hydrolysis of N-acetyl groups or oxidative N-dealkylation) and iii) the proposed mechanism that requires a monosubstituted hydrazine moiety.</p> |
| 616 | Halothane or analogue | <p>This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of halothane and analogues. These compounds may cause centrilobular necrosis in humans.</p> <p>Halothane and analogues are hydrofluorocarbons that are used as inhalational anaesthetic agents. They are known to affect many receptors (e.g. GABA-A, glycine, acetylcholine, serotonin, N-methyl-D-aspartate) but no theory has been formally established with regard to their site and mechanism of action [Tanner].</p> <p>Typical hepatotoxins include halothane, methoxyflurane, enflurane and fluroxene [Zimmerman]. Halothane, the prototype of this class, has been associated with biochemical evidence of liver damage and severe hepatic injury in up to 20% and 0.1% of recipients respectively [Zimmerman, Benjamin et al, Ludwig and Axelsen]. Albeit of low incidence, halothane-hepatitis has often been characterised by severe centrilobular necrosis, with an estimated mortality rate of 50% [Zimmerman, Benjamin et al]. Jaundice, fatty alterations and clinical signs of hypersensitivity (fever, eosinophilia, positive rechallenge with the offending agent, cross-reactivity with structural analogues and detection of antibodies) have been associated with the injury [Zimmerman, Benjamin et al, Lewis et al]. Additionally, lipid peroxidation, assessed by plasma F2-isoprostane concentrations has been demonstrated [Kharasch et al]. No dose-response relationship has been established. However, multiple exposures to the offending agent, obesity, genetic predisposition, hypoxia, hyperthyroidism and the use of P450 inducers are thought to enhance susceptibility [Zimmerman]. HCFC-123, employed as a substitute for ozone-depleting chlorofluorocarbons, methoxyflurane, enflurane, fluroxene and less frequently isoflurane have caused injuries that resemble those of halothane [Chaze, Lewis et al, Tucker et al, Turner et al].</p> <p>Increased alanine aminotransferase activity accompanied by necrosis and/or steatosis have been reproduced in several species with halothane and HCFC-123, and with other agents in rats [Zimmerman, Lind et al 1987, van Dyke, Chaze, Plummer et al, Berman et al, Tucker et al]. Liver toxicity has also been noted with 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol, a well documented metabolite of fluroxene [Tucker et al]. With the exception of the guinea pig model, extensive pretreatments and manipulations including hypoxia, fasting, GSH depletion, enzyme induction and/or prolonged exposure were required to potentiate the toxicity [Lind et al 1987]. However, no effects have been reported in guinea pigs under normal conditions, and in mice following prolonged exposure with isoflurane and enflurane respectively [Lunam et al, Baden et al].</p> <p>Allergic and/or toxic reactions and to a lesser extent hypoxia are thought to play a role in the pathogenesis [de Groot and Noll, Golembiewski]. The presumed mechanism involves an oxidative bioactivation, primarily mediated by CYP 2E1 and resulting in the formation of a fluoroacetyl intermediate susceptible to covalent binding to hepatic microsomal proteins, causing an immunologic response and subsequent toxicity [Kharasch and Thummel, Njoku et al, Lind et al 1995, Nelson and Trager, Christ et al]. Additionally, the toxic potential of these agents appears to be directly related to their degree of biotransformation with the highest</p> |

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| | | <p>rates measured for halothane and methoxyflurane [Zimmerman, Eger]. In the case of halothane and HCFC-123, a second hypothesis has been suggested. It implies a reductive pathway which yields, under anaerobic conditions, free radicals capable of damaging the hepatocytes [Zimmerman, Lind et al 1995, de Groot and Noll]. The current hypothesis holds that frequent slight injury is caused by the reductive pathway and that the immunologic reaction converts the usual slight injury to massive necrosis.</p> <p>The scope of the alert is based on the chemical features shared by the compounds discussed and on the mechanistic and metabolic considerations mentioned above.</p> |
| 617 | Halogenated hydrocarbon | <p>This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of halogenated aliphatic hydrocarbons. These compounds may cause necrosis and/or steatosis, and liver tumours in humans and experimental animals.</p> <p>Haloaliphatic hydrocarbons have been extensively used in the chemical and agricultural industry, in medicine, and domestically as solvents and chemical reagents [Zimmerman].</p> <p>These compounds are known occupational and environmental toxicants. Many of them are thought to possess a potential for causing liver damage [Zimmerman]. Acute hepatic injury in the form of centrilobular necrosis and macrovacuolar steatosis has been reported with the most toxic agents. Typical examples include carbon tetrachloride, widely employed as an experimental model for the study of certain hepatotoxic effects, chloroform, formerly used as an anaesthetic agent, tetrachloroethane, vinyl chloride and tetrachloroethylene. Chronic injury characterised by cirrhosis and/or hepatic carcinoma has also been described with the cited agents [Zimmerman].</p> <p>Necrosis, degeneration, steatosis, cirrhosis and liver tumours have been reproduced in many species with carbon tetrachloride. A dose-effect response has been established and biochemical changes have been noted within hours following the administration of the chemical [Zimmerman, Aleksunes et al, Litterst et al, IARC]. Chloroform, tetrachloroethane, vinyl chloride, tetrachloroethylene and several other halogenated compounds have shown similar injuries mainly in rats and mice [Constan et al, Larson et al, NTP 1983, Feron et al, Conolly et al, Maltoni and Lefemine, NTP 1986, IARC, Raucy et al, Zimmerman]. Chloroform has additionally been reported with extensive regenerative cell proliferation and cytolethality [Constan et al].</p> <p>The hepatotoxicity is thought to require metabolic activation of the parent compound primarily mediated by CYP2E1. Formation of intermediates occurs via dehalogenation, reduction, or reductive oxygenation, with certain hydrocarbons undergoing all three reaction types [Zimmerman, Constan et al, Raucy et al, Reynolds et al, Lash and Parker]. Current hypotheses hold that toxicity increases as the numbers of halogens, size and ease of homolytic cleavage of the molecule increase [Zimmerman]. Carbon tetrachloride toxicity has been attributed to its ability to undergo a reduction pathway leading to the trichloromethyl radical CCl_3^*. This radical can covalently bind to cellular molecules, impairing crucial cellular processes such as lipid metabolism, form adducts with DNA or generate oxidative stress. Depending on the oxygen concentration, the cited free radical may be converted to its peroxy form CCl_3COO^*, secondary radicals and by-products (e.g. phosgene, carbene-type products, and reactive aldehydes) also suspected to initiate the pathogenesis [Zimmerman, Weber et al]. There is a general agreement that lipid peroxidation in cell membranes, followed by ionic and enzymatic chaos plays a causative role [Zimmerman, Weber et al]. Regarding chloroform and halogenated olefins, there is evidence for the formation of an electrophilic rather than a free radical intermediate [Constan et al, Lash and Parker, van Duuren]. Phosgene has been proven to be the ultimate toxin for the former and several studies have supported the view that carcinogenicity stems from recurrent cytotoxicity and chronic cellular regeneration [Constan et al, Pohl et al]. A common mechanism for vinyl chloride and structural analogues may be through the formation of their corresponding epoxide, haloaldehyde or haloacylhalide derivatives [Zimmerman, van Duuren, Raucy et al, Lash and Parker].</p> |

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| | | <p>The scope of the alert is based on the physico-chemical considerations reviewed by Zimmerman and mentioned above. The alert includes i) chloro, bromo or iodo derivatives containing less than 5 carbon atoms and ii) any halogenated olefins on the basis of the toxicity data provided by Conolly et al. Halothane and analogues are excluded and constitute a separate alert by virtue of their toxicological response.</p> |
| 620 | 2-Arylacetic or 3-arylpropionic acid | <p>This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of 2-arylacetic and 3-arylpropionic acids.</p> <p>Arylacetic and arylpropionic acids constitute a widely used class of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) that have been associated with hepatotoxicity resembling acute or chronic active hepatitis. Several agents have known little clinical experience or have been withdrawn from the market because of the frequency and/or the severity of their effect. In most cases, the liver damage is thought to derive from an idiosyncratic metabolic and/or immune reaction, essentially independent of the dose [Zimmerman, Dong et al, Bailey and Dickinson]. Examples supporting the present alert include diclofenac [Boelsterli], bromfenac [Peters], benoxaprofen [Dahl and Ward], clometacin [Mamou and Levy], and oxaprozin [Kethu et al]. The toxic reactions, ranging from mild elevations in serum transaminases to severe hepatocellular and/or cholestatic injury, are relatively rare but important due to the potential for progression to fulminant hepatic failure. Jaundice, centrilobular necrosis, microvesicular steatosis, fibrosis, and symptoms suggestive of a hypersensitivity syndrome are clinical findings associated with the use of these agents [Zimmerman].</p> <p>The toxic response has been reproduced in rats treated with acute or chronic doses of benoxaprofen [Dahl and Ward]. High doses of pirofen and ibuprofen have been shown to significantly inhibit the mitochondrial beta-oxidation of fatty acids in mice, leading to microvesicular steatosis of the liver [Geneve et al, Freneaux et al]. Carcinogenicity studies with bromfenac have provided evidence for cytological alterations to hepatocytes in mice and rats. Acute exposure or sub-therapeutic doses of the same compound have only caused minor vacuolar changes in rats and mice and mild hepatic enzyme elevations in monkeys [Peters]. No major effects following acute or repeated exposure to other derivatives have been noted in traditional animal models [Falzon et al, Alcock, Macphail et al, El Sawy et al, Boelsterli]. However, this is not necessarily indicative for humans' case as supported by studies proving the toxicity of fenclozic acid in treated patients but not in mice, rats, dogs, and monkeys [Alcock].</p> <p>Derivation of modified protein adducts is thought to be essential to the hepatotoxicity induced by these agents. Two alternative metabolic pathways may play a causative role: hepatic acyl glucuronidation catalyzed by the uridine diphosphoglucosyl transferase (UGT) system, and acyl coenzyme A (acyl-CoA) formation. It is well established that acyl glucuronides are reactive electrophiles which can undergo covalent binding with plasma or tissue proteins via a transacylation or glycation mechanism [Li et al, Bailey and Dickinson]. In the former, protein adducts are formed by nucleophilic displacement of the glucuronic acid moiety. In the latter, intramolecular migration of the acyl residue allows opening of the glucuronic acid ring to create an aldehyde intermediate susceptible to nucleophilic attacks [Wang and Dickinson, Li]. Acyl conjugates have been detected for many derivatives including diclofenac also possibly generating toxicity via its quinone imine metabolite, and bromfenac, bearing additional toxicophores [Li et al, Wang and Dickinson, Dong et al, Wade et al, Boelsterli, Kirkman et al]. It has also been postulated that the reactivity of acyl-linked glucuronides is at least partly dependent on the degree of alpha-substitution, accounting for the greater effect of ibufenac (R2 = H), over that of ibuprofen (R2 = Me) [Wade et al]. Due to exposure to high acyl glucuronide concentrations, the liver is thought to be the preferential target organ. Dipeptidylpeptidase IV, UGTs, tubulin and biliary transporters are intra-hepatic proteins that have been shown to be involved in adduct formation [Bailey et al, Boelsterli]. This could explain in part the hepatocellular and/or cholestatic injury observed with this class.</p> |

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| | | The scope of this alert is based on i) the 2-arylacetic and 3-arylpropionic acid skeletons shared by the compounds discussed and ii) collated toxicity data and current view [Wade et al] suggesting that R2 can only be a hydrogen atom or a methyl group. |
| 653 | Organophosphorus di- or tri-ester | <p>This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of organophosphorus di- and tri-esters, and is based primarily on 28-day repeat-dose study data contributed by a Lhasa Limited member. Organophosphates and organophosphonates have been found to cause mixed injuries in the liver such as hepatocellular necrosis, hypertrophy or perilobular vacuolisation of hepatocytes, increases in liver weight, fatty changes in the liver, steatosis and elevations in the levels of transaminases and alkaline/acid phosphatases in experimental animals [MHLW 1995, MHLW 1998a, MHLW 1998b, Bhatnagar and Jain]. Little evidence on the hepatotoxicity of these compounds in humans has been found in the literature [Arao et al]. The mechanism of toxicity may be associated with the metabolic activation of these compounds although there is insufficient evidence to establish a comprehensive structure-activity relationship.</p> <p>Organophosphates and phosphonates have been extensively used as pesticides and insecticides and they are well known neurotoxic compounds. However, little evidence for human hepatotoxicity from occupational or accidental exposure to these chemicals was found in the literature. Accidental exposure of trichlorfon and methidathion in humans has been reported to cause accumulation in the liver [Arao et al].</p> <p>28-Day repeat-dose study of dibutyl phosphate [MHLW 1995], tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate [MHLW 1998a] and diphenyl 2-ethylhexyl phosphate [MHLW 1998b] in rats showed increases in liver weight, centrilobular hypertrophy of hepatocytes, vacuolisation of hepatocytes and steatosis at doses ranging from 100 to 1000 mg/kg/day. Phosphamidon orally dosed in mice caused midzonal necrosis and hypertrophy of hepatocytes, steatosis and disruption of hepatic enzymes and acid/alkaline phosphatases at doses up to 35 ppm over 30 and 60 days of dosing [Bhatnagar and Jain]. Centrilobular hepatic necrosis was also observed in rats dosed with tris(2,3-dibromopropyl) phosphate at doses ranging from 500 to 750 mg/kg bw [Soderlund et al].</p> <p>Multiple metabolic pathways are involved in the bioactivation of these compounds that may be responsible for their associated hepatotoxicity [Testa and Mayer, Mileson et al, Abdelsalam]: inhibition of carboxylesterases associated with disruption of hepatic metabolism, transfer and absorption of lipids across the endoplasmic reticulum [Saboori et al, Choudhari and Chakrabarti, Testa and Mayer], glutathione depletion mediated by glutathione S-transferase [Fujioka and Casida, Brakenhoff et al, Hutson et al] or formation of reactive oxygen species and subsequent oxidative damage via dealkylation of these compounds by microsomal mixed-function oxidases [Abdelsalam, Donniger et al, Lukaszewicz-Hussain and Moniuszko-Jakoniuk]. The nature of these reactions and the lack of a conclusive single mechanism of toxicity make it difficult to derive a single structure-activity relationship.</p> <p>The scope of this alert is defined by the structural features shared by organophosphates and organophosphonates. Di-aryl phosphoric and phosphonic acid esters have been excluded from the alert due to their lack of hepatotoxicity, which could be associated to the inability of these compounds to inhibit carboxylesterases [Saboori et al]. By contrast, di-alkyl esters of these acids display hepatotoxicity and are therefore included in the alert, although evidence suggests that such compounds do not inhibit carboxylesterases [Saboori et al, IPCS 2004, IPCS 1994]. Inorganic acids such as phosphoric and phosphonic acids and their sulphur analogues have also been excluded from the scope of the alert.</p> |
| 665 | Thiazole or derivative | This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of thiazole and its derivatives. They have been shown to cause an elevation of liver enzymes, jaundice, cholestasis and steatosis in humans [Jalota and Freston, Picard et al, Skandrani et al]. In experimental animals an alteration of liver function tests and histopathological changes were reported [Cho and Kim, Tada et al]. The proposed mechanism of toxicity is due to bioactivation of these compounds via thiazole 4,5-epoxidation followed by a ring scission and formation of a thioamide toxic metabolite |

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| | | <p>[Mizutani et al, Mizutani and Suzuki].</p> <p>Jaundice, cholestasis and bile duct injury were reported in patients treated with thiabendazole [Jalota and Freston, Manivel et al, Skandrani et al]. In some cases a progression to cirrhosis was observed [Roy et al, Skandrani et al]. An idiosyncratic immunoallergic reaction was suggested to be involved in thiabendazole hepatotoxicity [Manivel et al, Skandrani et al]. Ritonavir, an antiretroviral drug containing a thiazole ring, has also been implicated in liver toxicity. Elevation of liver enzymes and jaundice followed by liver failure were reported in a patient treated with 1200 mg/day of ritonavir [Picard et al]. Histopathological examination revealed microvesicular steatosis, cholestasis and fibrosis. The highest occurrence of hepatotoxicity in patients undergoing protease inhibitor therapy was associated with ritonavir particularly in HIV patients co-infected with hepatitis virus [Aceti et al].</p> <p>Liver toxicity has been reported in mice administered with 1.6% of body weight of thiabendazole for 13 weeks, while no effects on the liver were observed in those administered with 0.8% of body weight [Tada et al]. Hepatotoxicity manifested by an elevation of serum ALT and AST and increased liver weight with pathological changes in the liver such as sinusoidal dilation and enlargement of hepatocytes [Tada et al]. Rats treated with 116 mg/kg/day of 4-methylthiazole for 1-3 days developed liver necrosis [Cho and Kim]. In contrast, administration of 4,5-di- and 2,4,5-trimethyl substituted thiazoles did not result in toxic liver effects [Cho and Kim].</p> <p>The mechanism of toxicity for this class is thought to involve an epoxidation of the thiazole ring followed by ring scission leading to the formation of thioamide reactive metabolites. A good correlation between hepatotoxicity of 2-phenylthiazole derivatives and their proposed thioamide metabolites provides evidence for proposed toxicity mechanism [Mizutani and Suzuki]. Various 2 and 4 substituted derivatives of thiazoles were shown to undergo similar microsomal metabolism [Mizutani et al].</p> <p>The scope of this alert is based on the thiazole moiety shared by the compounds discussed, with restriction of position 5 to hydrogen to allow enzymatic epoxidation. This restriction is supported by the lack of ring oxidation and subsequent ring scission of meloxicam which has a methyl group in position 5 [Dalvie et al].</p> |
| 687 | Bisfuranoid mycotoxin or analogue | <p>This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of bisfuranoid mycotoxins, such as aflatoxins. These compounds are known to be naturally produced by fungi such as <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> [Goldblatt, Conning and Lansdown]. Exposure to these toxins can cause acute hepatitis, steatosis and liver necrosis in humans [Newberne, Apeagyei et al]. Liver injury by aflatoxins in animals can vary from steatosis to necrosis and fibrosis [Svoboda et al, Newberne]. The mechanism of toxicity involves the metabolic activation of these compounds to form the highly reactive 2,3-epoxide derivatives that may subsequently conjugate with DNA, proteins and RNA [Hsieh, Zimmerman]. Inhibition of RNA polymerase by aflatoxin reactive metabolites was proposed to be the cause of acute hepatic injury [Pong and Wogan]. Other effects of bisfuranoid mycotoxins such as mutagenicity and carcinogenicity are described elsewhere in the knowledge base.</p> <p>Aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) is one of the most potent hepatotoxins among this group [Zimmerman]. The main route of exposure of aflatoxins to humans and animals is orally by consuming contaminated nuts, cereals, spices and oilseeds stored under inappropriate condition with increased humidity and raised temperature allowing the growth of the fungi. Recent evidence of aflatoxin hepatotoxicity was reported in an outbreak of aflatoxin poisoning causing acute liver failures with fatalities in Kenya [Azziz-Baumgartner et al]. AFB1-lysine adducts were detected in serum of jaundiced patients and in most cases an association between adduct concentration and death after onset of jaundice was established. Evidence of the increased toxicity of aflatoxins due to malnutrition is reported in children with kwashiorkor (a nutritional deficiency illness). High concentrations of aflatoxin B1 and G1, G2 and M2 were found at the</p> |

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| | | <p>biopsy of the livers of children from African countries [Apeagyei et al, Coulter et al]. The involvement of aflatoxin poisoning in the development of a Reye's-like syndrome in children has also been proposed, the correlation of the presence of aflatoxin in liver specimens and various degrees of liver injury such as fatty liver and fibrosis and cirrhosis was noted [Dvorackova et al, Harwig et al].</p> <p>Hepatotoxicity of this chemical class has been observed in a number of species. The variability in the susceptibility of animals to aflatoxin poisoning has been reported with swine and poultry being the most and sheep the least susceptible to aflatoxins [Newberne]. Liver toxicity in rats treated with sterigmatocystin (0.2 mg/kg/d, 30 days) was observed in the form of degenerated parenchymal hepatocytes, necrosis and proliferation of Kupffer cells [Sivakumar et al]. In chicks sterigmatocystin (i.p. injection 10-14 mg/kg) has been reported to cause liver haemorrhagic necrosis with fibroblastic proliferation [Sreemannarayana et al]. Canine aflatoxicosis was reported with the cause of death, attributed to the intoxication from the consumption of aflatoxin-contaminated dog food [Newman et al]. Histopathological findings included fatty liver, biliary hyperplasia and portal fibrosis of the liver [Newman et al]. Periportal parenchymal cell necrosis was observed in the liver of rats following oral administration of 0.45-3.78 mg/kg [Svoboda et al]. The same authors reported extensive hemorrhagic liver necrosis in monkeys after single oral exposure (3 mg/kg) or intraperitoneal injection (2.5 mg/kg) of pure aflatoxin B1 [Svoboda et al]. Severe hepatic necrosis was observed during necropsy of horses fed with corn contaminated with aflatoxins B1, B2 and M1 in concentrations of 114, 10 and 6 mg/kg respectively [Vesonder et al].</p> <p>The mechanism of hepatic toxicity of bisfuranoid mycotoxins is intrinsic, and activation in the liver by cytochrome P450 enzymes to the 2,3 epoxide is required for acute and chronic liver toxicity [Hsieh, Zimmerman]. Inhibition of RNA polymerase by reactive metabolites of aflatoxins leading to suppression of RNA synthesis and cell death was suggested to be responsible for acute toxicity of aflatoxins and shown to be dose-dependent [Pong and Wogan]. Necrosis and steatosis are presumed to be secondary to RNA inhibition [Zimmerman]. An alternative mechanism for steatosis has been proposed to be via formation of covalent adducts of aflatoxins metabolites with lysine residues on low density lipoprotein and affect normal lipid metabolism [Amaya-Farfan]. Specific receptors on peripheral cells are unable to recognise these modified lipoproteins and they are returned to the liver where they accumulate in hepatocytes [Amaya-Farfan]. The shape of the compound as a whole can have an influence on the toxicity: mycotoxins with angular type ring systems were found to be more toxic than ones containing linear system in chick embryonal hepatocytes [Terao and Ito]. The compound's solubility and as consequence its bioavailability for activation was an additional factor [Terao and Ito].</p> <p>The scope of alert is based on the presence of bisfuranoid ring structure where a 2,3 double bond is required for formation of a reactive epoxide. Compounds containing a saturated 2,3 bond are included as they can also be metabolised in some species to the unsaturated compounds [Roebuck et al].</p> |
| 819 | Conjugated alkene | <p>This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of conjugated alkenes. Liver toxicity data in humans is limited and based mainly on changes of liver enzymes levels. In animal studies, conjugated alkenes have been reported to cause liver injury observed as steatosis, hepatocellular hypertrophy, necrosis, increased levels of hepatic enzymes, depletion of glutathione levels and increases in absolute liver weight. Although the mechanism of hepatotoxicity is not fully understood conjugated alkenes are considered to be metabolised in the liver by cytochromes P450 mainly into reactive epoxides which form adducts with cellular macromolecules of the liver and lead to intrinsic adverse hepatic effects.</p> <p>Occupational exposure to styrene leading to liver toxicity in humans was reported in some studies [Harkonen et al] but not in others [Lorimer et al]. Liver damage assessment in human is based on changes in serum levels of enzymes, biomarkers of liver dysfunction.</p> |

Conjugated alkenes were also described to cause liver damage in laboratory animals. Styrene inhalation exposure of adult male rats for 11 weeks (300 ppm, 6 hr/day, 5 days/week) induced parenchymal hydropic degeneration, **steatosis** and congestion [Vainio et al]. Decrease of free glutathione content and increase of activity of phase II metabolism enzymes (uridine 5'-diphospho-glucuronosyltransferase) were also observed. Hepatotoxicity in mice after repeated styrene inhalation for 14 days (0, 125, 250, or 500 ppm, 6 h/day) was characterised by severe haemorrhagic centrilobular hepatic necrosis and congestion in moribund animals at the two highest doses [Morgan et al 1993]. Male mice were more susceptible than females. In affected animals changes in serum alanine aminotransferase, sorbitol dehydrogenase and absolute liver weight were also observed. Species differences were also reported, where mice were found to be more susceptible than rats to styrene-induced hepatotoxicity [Cruzan et al]. alpha-Methylstyrene, despite its structural similarity to styrene, has been reported to cause very weak and mild hepatotoxic effects in rats (0, 600, or 1000 ppm) and mice (0, 600, 800, or 1000 ppm) respectively after inhalation exposure for 12 days (6 h/day, 5 days/week) [Morgan et al 1999]. Increased absolute liver weight in mice and rats, and decreased hepatic glutathione in mice were reported in exposed animals. Repeated oral exposure of rats to alpha-methylstyrene for 43 days (0, 40, 200, 1000 mg/kg/day) induced mild liver damage manifested as acidophilic changes in the hepatocytes at two highest doses and increase of absolute liver weight at top dose [NITE 1996]. Chloroprene has been shown to induce increases of absolute liver weight, in serum activities of alanine aminotransferase, glutamate dehydrogenase and sorbitol dehydrogenase as well as centrilobular to random hepatocellular necrosis in rats (0, 32, 80, 200, or 500 ppm) and mice (0, 12, 32, 80, or 200 ppm) in inhalation toxicological studies (6 h/day, 5 days/week, 16 days) [NTP 1998]. A long term inhalation exposure of mice to 1,3-butadiene (625, or 1250 ppm, 6 h/day, 5 days/week, 61 weeks) lead to a significant increase in liver necrosis compared to control groups [NTP 1984].

The mechanism of hepatotoxicity of this class is thought to result from hepatic metabolic activation by cytochromes P450 into the chemically reactive epoxides. It was shown that styrene metabolised to styrene 7,8-oxide [Sumner and Fennell], an electrophilic epoxide, that forms adducts with cellular macromolecules [Yuan et al]. Similarly 1,3-butadiene, chloroprene and isoprene were shown to be respectively transformed into epoxybutene [Kirman et al], (1-chloroethenyl)oxirane [Munter et al] and isoprene oxide/2-isopropenyloxirane [Hurst] which are believed to be able to bind covalently to cellular macromolecules of the liver and lead to hepatotoxicity. These studies also showed that the metabolism of styrene, 1,3-butadiene, chloroprene and isoprene appear to follow the same enzymatic pathways in all species, including humans. However, species variability in the rates of formation and detoxification of reactive metabolites may explain the difference of susceptibility to liver damage between species.

The scope of this alert has been defined by our understanding of the metabolic fate of this class of chemical as substrates of hepatic cytochromes P450. Oxidative metabolism of conjugated alkenes leading to the formation of reactive epoxides requires unsubstituted terminal carbon. Substitution on the allylic carbon is restricted to methyl or alkyl that branched out further away from the allylic bond based on weak liver damage for alpha-methylstyrene [Morgan et al 1999, NITE 1996] and positive results in hepatotoxicity studies for 4-methyl-2,4-diphenyl-1-pentene [NITE 2007]. Fluorine, chlorine, bromide and alkyl groups are allowed on the benzene ring given that none was thought to be able to prevent the epoxidation of conjugated alkenes from occurring. On the contrary, a SAR study of para-halogenated styrene analogues in CYP2E1 transgenic cells showed that cytotoxicity increased with regard to styrene [Chung et al]. Vinyl toluene has also reported to cause liver damage [NTP 2006]. In contrast hydroxy substituents on the benzene ring have been excluded from this alert on the basis of absence of liver damage in rat exposed to 4-isopropenyphenol [NITE 2002] and alternative metabolism of 4 vinylphenol [Carlson et al, Vogie et al]. The same substitution pattern is allowed on the vinyl group by analogy with the benzene ring.